

The Evolution of Cuvature of Blazar Spectral Energy Distribution

in The Fermi Era

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摘要

银河系外的伽玛射线辐射源主要是耀变体。耀变体的宽波段能谱是明显弯曲的。而能谱弯曲的起源及其演化一直没能得到很好的解释。显然，耀变体能谱的曲率与非热辐射电子分布的曲率是直接相关的。在粒子的加速和冷却框架下，本文研究了耀变体多波段能谱曲率的起源及其演化。本文通过采用单区辐射模型+对数抛物线电子能谱拟合了一个耀变体样本的多波段能谱，发现电子能谱曲率和能谱峰值能量呈现很好地反相关。这一结果表明非热电子的分布可以在统计加速框架下得到很好解释。当我们进一步把耀变体分成蝎虎天体和平谱射电类星体两类时，我们发现，上述电子能谱曲率和能谱峰值能量的反相关主要是蝎虎天体主导的，而平谱射电类星体几乎没有相关，甚至呈现正相关。通过与粒子加速和冷却模型的对比，我们认为，从统计上来说，蝎虎天体喷流的电子可能处在粒子（统计）加速主导阶段；而平谱射电类星体喷流的电子演化到冷却主导的一个近乎平衡态的阶段。本文进一步研究了能谱曲率与产生伽玛射线辐射强弱间的可能关联。我们构建了一个被费米卫星探测到的蝎虎天体样本和未被费米卫星探测到蝎虎天体对比样本。我们研究发现，相比较未被费米卫星探测到蝎虎天体，被费米卫星探测到的蝎虎天体具有较小能谱曲率；即便去除了多普勒放大效应的影响，这一个结果仍然存在。我们同时发现了曲率和康普顿主导因子的相关性。我们又选取了两个蝎虎天体（PKS 0048-09 和 S5 0716+714），它们具有相同的同步辐射光度，但却明显不同的伽玛射线光度。对它们的能谱拟合发现，除了辐射区尺度和能谱曲率以外，它们具有相同的喷流参数。其中 PKS 0048-09 具有更强的伽玛射线辐射、更小的能谱曲率和更小的辐射区尺度。以上所有结果表明，强伽玛射线辐射蝎虎天体可能有更加致密的喷流，这导致了更大光子能谱密度从而产生更强伽玛射线辐射，而更致密的喷流也导致了更有效的粒子加速从而产生了更小的能谱曲率。除了能谱的峰值频率、光度和康普顿主导因子以外，能谱曲率是描述宽波段能谱的第四个重要参量。它的性质对于研究耀变体辐射的物理性质起到重要作用（比如粒子加速等）。未来的 TeV 望远镜 CTA 与 GeV 光谱相结合，将会提供更好的研究耀变体起源和演化的机会。

关键词：活动星系核；耀变体；非热辐射；粒子加速

Abstract

The blazars are powerful γ -ray emitters and dominate the extragalactic sky. Their broadband spectra are significantly curved and the evolution of spectral curvature has not been well understood. The spectral curvature in blazar spectral energy distribution (SED) should be related to an intrinsic curvature of emitting nonthermal electron distribution (EED). This work investigates the origin and evolution of the spectral curvature of blazar SED in context of particle acceleration and cooling mechanisms. It is found that a one-zone log-parabolic inverse Compton (IC) model adequately explains the broadband SEDs of Fermi bright blazars, suggesting that there is a strong stochastic component in the particle acceleration as revealed through an inverse correlation between the curvature and peak energy of log-parabolic EED. However the signature correlation is only found for BL Lac objects (BL Lacs), while FSRQs do not show signature of acceleration, that might be attributed to dominant radiative cooling due to stronger magnetic field and an additional external Compton (EC) component. Therefore, it is suggested that the curvature of underlying EED, in a combined acceleration and cooling scenario, evolves in a purely acceleration dominated regime in BL Lacs, whereas the curvature of FSRQs evolve in a cooling dominated phase with conditions nearly corresponding to steady state. The intrinsic difference between Fermi detected BL Lacs (FBLs) and non-detected BL Lacs (NFBLs) has also been studied and it is found that FBLs show smaller spectral curvature than the NFBLs. It has been found that curvature and Compton dominance (CD) of BL Lacs is related. Two BL Lacs PKS 0048-09 and S5 0716+714 have similar synchrotron luminosity but a different γ -ray luminosity. Their quasi-simultaneous SEDs can be modeled with same physical jet parameters except the source size and EED curvature parameter. PKS 0048-09 with higher CD manifests small curvature, that can be explained if there is a phenomenal positive relationship between curvature parameter and the source size. This shows that for BL Lac objects with at a given synchrotron power, FBLs might have relatively compact jets which make the acceleration and cooling more efficient, leading to a smaller curvature and higher CD. The curvature is an important parameter of the SED in addition to peak frequency, bolometric power, and CD, and, therefore, it can be considered a fourth parameter of blazar sequence. The Fermi LAT γ -ray spectra of

bright blazars shows curvature, suggesting that all blazars may have curved spectra. The curvature at high energy is important and may reveal the underlying physical conditions in the jet. The future TeV telescope CTA combined with Fermi GeV spectra can provide the opportunity to study the origin of curvature and its evolution in blazars in more details.

Keywords: active galactic nuclei; blazars; non-thermal radiation; particle acceleration

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Symbols

Symbol	Description	Units
pc	parsec	3.086×10^{18} cm
ev	Electron volt	1.602×10^{-12} erg
M_{\odot}	Mass of sun	2×10^{33} g
L_{\odot}	Luminosity of sun	3.826×10^{33} erg s ⁻¹
m_e	Mass of electron	9.1×10^{-28} g
e	Charge of electron	4.8×10^{-10} esu
m_p	Mass of proton	1.67×10^{-24} g
c	Speed of light	3×10^{10} cm s ⁻¹
G	Gravitational constant	6.67×10^{-8} cm ³ g ⁻¹ s ⁻²
h	Planck's constant	6.626×10^{27} erg s
k	Boltzmann constant	1.38×10^{-16} erg K ⁻¹
σ	Stefan-Boltzmann constant	5.67×10^{-5} erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻² deg ⁻⁴
σ_T	Thomson cross-section area	6.65×10^{-25} cm ²
M	Mass of black hole	M_{\odot}
Γ	Jet Lorentz factor	A unitless quantity
δ	Relativistic Doppler factor	A unitless quantity
γ	Electron Lorentz factor	A unitless quantity
E	Electron energy	$\gamma m_e c^2$
x	Photon energy	A unitless quantity
ν	Frequency	Hz
β	Spectral curvature	A unitless quantity
I_{ν}	Spectral Intensity	erg cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sterad ⁻¹ Hz ⁻¹
u	Energy Density	erg cm ⁻³
z	Redshift	A unitless quantity

Chapter 1 Active Galactic Nuclei

“Man must rise above the Earth—to the top of the atmosphere and beyond—for only thus will he fully understand the world in which he lives.”

Socrates

1.1 Introduction to AGN

Active galactic Nuclei (AGN) are the compact bright cores of active galaxies and dominate the observed continuum emission. Usually a typical galaxy contains an order of a trillion stars, however some galaxies show bright centers with “*quasi-stellar*” appearance. Starting with the discovery of 3C 273 in 1963 ([Schmidt, 1963](#)), it has been found that these quasi-stellar objects in the heart of galaxies are actually AGN. The spectrum of a normal galaxy is essentially the composite thermal spectrum of inhabitant stars. It is suggested based on motion of stars in the central region of the galaxy that almost all regular galaxies host a *supermassive black hole* (SMBH) in the center. In active galaxies, the central SMBH accretes the surrounding matter and shines the central region. Only a few % of all galaxies are active, suggesting that these galaxies host accreting black holes (BHs). The mass of SMBHs ranges from order of 10^6 to $10^9 M_{\odot}$ and a typical AGN with $10^8 M_{\odot}$ BH emits the radiation at 10^{46} erg s^{-1} . Such high luminosity can not explained by composite stellar radiation of the galaxy.

The AGN emit radiation across the whole electromagnetic spectrum, making them interesting objects for multiwavelength studies. The radiation from the AGN can not be attributed to the stellar component of a galaxy and related to accretion of surrounding matter onto SMBH due to strong gravitational field. The in-flowing gas loses angular momentum and heats up while falling onto black hole (BH). The in-flowing gas is ionized in this process as energy is released as heat and radiation. The electrons feel the radiation pressure through Thomson scattering while the massive protons feel the gravitational

pull by the central BH. Due to a balance between an outward radiation force and inward gravitational force, the maximum luminosity for a BH of mass M , in case of a spherical accretion, becomes

$$L_E \leq \frac{4\pi G c m_p}{\sigma_T} M, \quad (1.1)$$

called Eddington luminosity in units of erg s^{-1} . The accretion power observed in the form of radiation L is only a fraction of total accretion power. The accretion power L of a BH is

$$L = \dot{M} c^2, \quad (1.2)$$

where \dot{M} is the mass accretion rate in units of g s^{-1} . If, for in-falling mass m on an object of mass M and radius R , all the potential energy $\Delta E = GMm/R$ is converted to radiation, the accretion power becomes

$$L = \frac{GM\dot{M}}{R}. \quad (1.3)$$

It is important to note that unlike compact neutron stars or white dwarfs, BHs do not have a sharp surfaces. However with known BH mass M and assuming that accretion luminosity is equal to Eddington luminosity, i.e., $L \sim L_E$, the accretion rate \dot{M} can be estimated. The accretion process in stellar mass BH X-ray binaries (XRBs), which have stellar mass BHs are similar to the one in AGN. Thus accretion of matter on to a compact object provides the source of energy from stellar up to galactic BHs, and describes the high luminosity that can not be explained by other sources of energy release.

1.1.1 Components of AGN

Typically AGN are compact objects with a size of ~ 1 pc (Krolik, 1999). The central AGN in the heart of galaxy is composed of several main components other than the SMBH (Kembhavi et al., 1999) and accretion disk, as shown in Figure 1.1. From observational perspective, not all the AGN show all the components. However an AGN typically consists of following components:

- SMBH
- Accretion disk
- Broad Line Region (BLR)
- Narrow Line Region (NLR)
- Dusty Torus
- Relativistic Jet

Figure 1.1 The graphical illustration AGN components. The central SMBH is surrounded by accretion disk, broad and narrow line clouds, an obscuring torus of dust, and a relativistic jet emanating from the vicinity of SMBH. Adapted from [Urry et al. \(1995\)](#).

Supermassive Black Hole:

Essentially a BH is an object where the escape velocity becomes infinity. A SMBH is the central engine that resides in the heart of AGN. The galaxy is observable from its outer edge up to Schwarzschild radius that defines the size of BH, as given by

$$R_s = 2 \frac{GM}{c^2}. \quad (1.4)$$

BH mass determination in AGN have been difficult using dynamics of central stars due to strong continuum emission. Recently, Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) team imaged the $6.5 \times 10^9 M_\odot$ BH in the nearby galaxy M87 using very long baseline interferometry (VLBI) technique ([Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration et al., 2019](#)), as shown in Figure 1.2. This important discovery marked the first observational evidence of existence of BHs.

Accretion Disk:

The AGN are powered by mass accretion on to BH. When the BH pulls the surrounding material, the in-falling gas has to lose angular momentum. Thus, the in-flowing gas naturally forms a disk as it spirals into BH, called accretion disk. As the gas flows into the BH, the disk heats up due to viscous forces and the energy is released as heat and radiation. A rough estimate of the brightness temperature T_b can be made by assuming the disk as a

Figure 1.2 The black hole at the center of M87 as imaged by ETH. A bright ring formed as light bends in the intense gravity around a black hole. Adapted from [Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration et al. \(2019\)](#).

simple blackbody and given by

$$T_b = \sqrt[4]{\frac{L}{4\pi R^2 \sigma}}. \quad (1.5)$$

The typical disk temperature in AGN is of order $\sim 10^5$ K which corresponds to UV emission. In case of XRBs the temperature is of order of $\sim 10^7$ K and their emission, therefore, dominates in X-rays. The *Shakura-Sunyaev* standard disk model ([Shakura et al., 1973](#)) assumes a geometrically thin optically thick accretion disk. The thin disk can be considered as a system of concentric thermal rings and the spectrum of the disk is superimposed spectra of these individual rings. Thus, the temperature has a radial profile $T(r)$, as given by

$$T(r) = \left[\frac{3R_s L_d}{16\pi\eta\sigma_{\text{MB}} R^3} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{3R_s}{R}} \right) \right]^{1/4}. \quad (1.6)$$

The accretion disk luminosity is an important parameter to constrain the accretion rate or the BH mass. The disk luminosity L_d is given by

$$L_d = \eta_d \dot{M} c^2, \quad (1.7)$$

where $\dot{M} c^2$ is the accretion power and η_d is the fraction of that power released as disk luminosity. Nominally $\eta_d = 0.1$, showing that accretion is the most effective method of energy conversion in astrophysical sources as efficiency in case of nuclear burning is ~ 0.01 . Occasionally a hot sheath of electrons with temperature $\geq 10^7$ K is considered as a source of X-ray emission of the AGN.

Line Emission Region:

The broad line region (BLR) consists of rapid moving dense gas clouds with density $n \sim 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ in vicinity of BH at a distance $0.01 - 0.1 \text{ pc}$. As BLR is illuminated by the hot disk continuum photons, it radiates the line emission in optical and UV band. Due to fast orbital motion of clouds, the lines are Doppler broadened with line width typically ranging from 5000 km s^{-1} to 10000 km s^{-1} . The line emission of particles moving towards us is blue-shifted, while the emission of receding particles is red-shifted. The line emission includes Lyman- α , suggesting that BLR is dominantly composed of atomic Hydrogen. The BLR is clumpy and dense, however its geometry is still not clear.

At very large distances ($\sim 100 \text{ pc}$) the molecular gas in the narrow line region (NLR) moves with relatively smaller density (n is in the range $10^3 - 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$), producing the line emission with smaller dispersion velocity in the range $1000 - 2000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The emission lines also include the forbidden lines, suggesting that NLR particles are also stimulated by collision. The NLR gas belongs to inner region of galactic disk.

Dusty Torus:

The dusty torus is the extended obscuring structure dominating at pc scale distance, typically in the range $1 - 10 \text{ pc}$. The torus reprocess the AGN continuum emission from UV to IR due to absorption. One important parameter is the covering factor of torus structure. It is found that roughly 50% of the AGN emission is absorbed by the torus.

Relativistic Jets:

The dawn of radio astronomy in the 20th century completely changed our understanding of the extragalactic sky, in particular AGN. Many AGN show the powerful relativistic jets emitting radio emission. These relativistic jets are highly collimated outflows of relativistic plasma and can travel very large distances without disturbance. The jets have been observed in a wide range of astrophysical systems including young stellar objects (YSOs), gamma ray bursts (GRBs), and AGN. Usually astrophysical jets are composed of non-thermal plasma and an ambient magnetic field that plays an important role in the launching, collimation, and dissipation of these jets. The radio jets in some AGN are observed to be very bright, extending to kpc inter-stellar medium (ISM) or even up to Mpc distances in the inter-galactic medium (IGM). [Begelman et al. \(1984\)](#) presented a review of characteristics and features of these extended radio jets and their connection to

central engine, suggesting that these extended objects are powerful synchrotron radiation sources. However not all AGN show *radio loudness*¹ and typically 10% of AGN are found to be radio loud. Based on absolute luminosity and/or morphology of radio emission, the AGN are classified into different classes. The origin of discrepancy between radio loud and radio quiet AGN is not well understood.

Figure 1.3 The 4.9 GHz VLA radio map of quasar 3C 175. The jet shows several components including a core M, the hotspots C and O and several knots from D to L. Extracted from (Bridle et al., 1994).

Since the VLBI can resolve the structure of radio jets, the radio loud AGN have been important objects of study in the last several decades. (Bridle et al., 1994) presented the Very Large Array (VLA) radio maps of 12 extended quasars from the 3CR catalog at 4.9 GHz. For example, the extended jet in the quasar 3C 175 shows a core-jet structure with several knots, ending with hotspots, as shown in Figure 1.3. The core show a flat radio spectrum with spectral index < 0.5 . Based on the morphology of the radio jet, AGN can be mainly divided in to *Fanaroff-Riley I* (FR I) and *Fanaroff-Riley II* (FR II) radio galaxies (Fanaroff et al., 1974). The FR Is show extended core-jet structure with lobes. There jets are symmetric and edge-darkened. FR IIs are high luminosity sources and show knotty structure with hotspots. These edge-brightened sources are well collimated and often show one-sided jet. Both FR I and FR II sources show narrow line emission and called *Narrow Line Radio Galaxies* (NLRGs).

The observations of extended radio jet structure enabled the study the jet dynamics at various scales, as shown in Figure 1.4. The kpc size jet shows an extended jet with a bright

¹Radio Loudness R_L is described as the ratio of 5 GHz radio luminosity L_{5GHz} to optical luminosity L_O , i.e., $R_L = L_{5GHz}/L_O$.

Figure 1.4 The radio jet structure of in M87 from kpc to sub-pc size scale (left to right). The kpc jet shows the dominant lob-jet structure, while the < 0.1 pc jet shows a resolved radio core and jet components. Taken from [Blandford et al. \(2019\)](#).

core and lobes which present the shock produced by the jet in the ISM. An older shock, perpendicular to the lobe-jet structure is also visible. Figure 1.4 shows that the radio jets have different morphology at different distance scales. ETH resolved the innermost part of radio jet of a distant quasar 3C 279 hosting a SMBH with mass $\sim 10^9 M_{\odot}$, as shown in Figure 1.5. The base of the radio jet is visible and it is assumed that the bulk of variable high energy emission arises from the inner region of the jet.

Typically there are two main mechanisms of jet production from the BH: (i) *Blandford-Znajek* (BZ) mechanism ([Blandford et al., 1977](#)) and; (ii) *Blandford-Payne* (BP) mechanism. In BZ mechanism, rotational energy of a spinning Kerr BH might be extracted by magnetized accretion flow channeled into a poynting flux dominated jet. In BP method the accretion power is released from a non-rotating BH and injected into the jet supported by magnetic field of infalling matter. Although both mechanisms can produce the collimated jets, the BZ mechanism is supported by observational evidence, as the jet power is found to be higher than accretion power ([Chen, 2018](#); [Ghisellini et al., 2014](#)). Despite the study over last four decades, the main aspects of relativistic jets, including launching, acceleration, collimation, composition, and dissipation are far from being fully understood (see, e.g. [Romero et al., 2017](#), for a review.).

The jet power L_j is an important parameter to study the formation and propagation mechanisms of relativistic jets. The jet power L_j can be constrained from the accretion

Figure 1.5 The illustration of multiwavelength jet structure of 3C 279 in April 2017. The observing epochs, telescope arrays, and wavelengths are noted at each panel. Credits: ETH Collaboration.

power as

$$L_j = \eta_j \dot{M} c^2, \quad (1.8)$$

where η_j is the fraction of accretion power converted to jet. Thus the accretion and jet power are related as

$$L_j = \frac{\eta_j}{\eta_d} L_d. \quad (1.9)$$

In the standard accretion theory $\eta_d \approx \eta_j \sim 0.1$, suggesting that $L_j \sim L_d$. However mass accretion rate \dot{M} is a key parameter of jet physics and, depending on surrounding conditions of the SMBH, its value may be different for different sources. The mass accretion rate can be constrained from jet power L_j , that can be constrained through accretion disk (Celotti et al., 1997, 2008; Ghisellini et al., 2009b). For AGN with $L_j > L_d$, the jets are important (Ghisellini et al., 2014).

1.1.2 Unification Model of AGN

Ideally many types of galaxies host AGN. These mainly include *Seyfert Galaxies* which are spiral galaxies with line emission, *Radio Galaxies* that show extended radio emission, and distant *Quasars* showing a quasi-stellar appearance. The fact that all components are not observed in AGN leads to a plethora of objects. The *AGN Zoo* has many classes of objects based on observational parameters. Broadly speaking, the AGN are divided two main groups: *Type 1* and *Type 2*; based on the spectral line emission (Urry et al., 1995). The AGN continuum luminosity, radio loudness R_L and broad emission line strength are

Figure 1.6 The illustration of an orientation based unification model of AGN (Urry et al., 1995). The type of AGN observed depends on the viewing angle. Imported from Beckmann et al. (2012).

important parameters for classification of AGN. Based on R_L , the AGN are classified as *Radio Loud* AGN ($R_L > 10$) or *Radio Quiet* AGN ($R_L < 10$).

Type 1 AGN usually have bright continua and show strong optical broad emission lines from hot high velocity BLR gas located deep in the gravitational well of the BH. *Radio Quiet Type 1* AGN include *Seyfert 1* galaxies with moderately bright cores at low luminosity end, while *Quasi Stellar Objects* (QSOs) with bright cores at high luminosity end. *Radio Loud Type 1* AGN mainly consists of low luminosity *Broad Line Radio Galaxies* (BLRGs), and *Flat Spectrum Radio Quasars* (FSRQs) at high luminosity which show flat power-law radio spectra. *Type 2* AGN usually show weaker continua and narrow emission lines from the slow moving distant NLR clouds. *Radio Loud Type 2* are classified as *Narrow Line Radio Galaxies* (NLRGs), while their radio quiet counterparts are *Seyfert 2* galaxies.

Additionally, but importantly, a small class of jetted AGN dominated by the jet emission is called *Type 0* AGN. The *Radio Quiet Type 0* AGN class includes *Broad Absorption Line Quasars* (BALs), whereas the *Radio Loud Type 0* population is known as *Blazars*. Blazars are classified as *BL Lac objects* (BL Lacs) or *FSRQs* according to whether the

Figure 1.7 The AGN spectral energy distribution (SED) of jetted and non-jetted AGN. The solid black curve represents the total emission of non-jetted AGN. The jetted AGN SED is also shown for a high synchrotron peaked (HSP) blazar Mrk 421 and low synchrotron peaked (LSP) blazar 3C 454.3. Adopted from [Padovani et al. \(2017\)](#).

rest-frame equivalent width of their broad emission lines was greater than (for FSRQs) or smaller than (for BL Lacs) 5 \AA . The FSRQs are further divided into different classes based on variability, polarization or radio core dominance. BL Lacs usually show only narrow line emission. Despite the variety of observed phenomena in AGN, it is assumed that all AGN have similar nature and structure, and unified under an orientation model—the so called *AGN Unification Model*, as shown in Figure 1.6. [Begelman et al. \(1984\)](#) discussed the theoretical prospects of different AGN classes in terms of jet speed and accretion mechanism. However, the *AGN Unification Model* suggests that the observed differences in AGN classes naturally arise due to orientation of jet with respect to the line of sight. See [Urry et al. \(1995\)](#) and [Padovani et al. \(2017\)](#) for a overview of AGN phenomenology and unification scheme based on multiwavelength emission properties.

Since the AGN are broadband continuum and line emitters, they are perfect objects for multiwavelength studies. Figure 1.7 shows the composite SED of jetted and non-jetted AGN components emitting at different wavelengths. At radio bands the synchrotron jet emission dominates, however the emission at higher energies could be dominated by thermal or nonthermal continuum emission depending on the type of AGN. In non-jetted AGN, the IR emission is dominated by thermal emission of heated dust. Their optical-UV emission shows a bump due to thermal emission of hot disk, called *Big Blue Bump* (BBB). Any variability in the disk emission will reverberate through BLR and NLR and can be used to constrain the BH mass, in a technique called reverberation mapping ([Kaspi](#)

et al., 2007). The AGN shows power-law (PL) X-ray spectra with spectral index ~ 1.8 , however its origin is still under debate. It is usually assumed to arise due to comptonization of accretion disk photons by energetic electrons in the corona. Thus, a broadband SED of AGN can be used to constrain the emission models.

1.2 Blazars

Blazars are jetted AGN which show bright radio cores with flat spectra, extreme variability at all frequencies, and a high degree of polarization. The term blazar was coined in 1978 at Pittsburgh Conference on BL Lacs (Blandford et al., 1978). The FSRQs and BL Lacs make up the blazar class of AGN and their emission is dominated by non-thermal jet. The BL Lacs mostly dominate the low redshift sky ($z \leq 1$) whereas the FSRQs are detected up to very large redshifts ($z \sim 7$), making them important objects to study cosmic evolution history of AGN and their host galaxies. Blazars are the AGN with jet pointed within few degrees to our earth (Urry et al., 1995). Due to Doppler boosting effect, their jet non-thermal emission is enhanced. Blazars are a small fraction of AGN and their jet emission shines over the thermal stellar emission of host galaxies and AGN continua. The blazars are broadband emitters from radio up to very high energy (VHE) γ -rays and the γ -ray emission usually dominate their radiative power. Blazar emission is highly variable on a very short timescales, while the variability timescales are frequency dependent. Since the blazar emission is dominated by relativistic jets, they can be used to constrain the physical models of jet production and emission. Boettcher et al. (2012) discussed all the aspects of relativistic jets in blazars, including jet formation, propagation, and dissipation models.

Due to bright broadband emission, blazars are perfectly suitable for multiwavelength studies. Occasionally, the coordinated multiwavelength observations of a large blazar sample are conducted to obtain the simultaneous SEDs of blazars (for example, Giommi et al., 2012b). The observed broadband blazar SEDs is usually represented in $\log(\nu F_\nu)$ vs $\log(\nu)$ plots and clearly shows two characteristic humps (Abdo et al., 2010a; Giommi et al., 2012b). The advantage of this representation is that it gives the power of the source per logarithmic frequency interval which shows the total power in a frequency band and different bands can, thus, be compared. In the AGN frame, an equivalent representation would be $\log(\nu L_\nu)$ vs $\log(\nu)$. As an example, the variable multiwavelength SED of a blazar 3C 454.3 is shown in Figure 1.8. The SED shows the two signature bumps

Figure 1.8 The broadband SED of 3C 454.3 showing quiescent, flare and post flaring state. Extracted from [Shah et al. \(2017\)](#).

and the evolution of a powerful high energy flare. These low energy bump arises due to synchrotron and the high energy one is attributed to inverse Compton (IC) emission ([Maraschi et al., 1992](#)), which will be discussed in next chapter. Usually a simultaneous SED of a blazar at a single epoch can highlight the underlying physical conditions. The time resolved SED modeling of a flaring blazar can be used to investigate the physical origin of spectral changes (see, e.g. [Hu et al., 2020](#); [Yan et al., 2016](#); [Zhu et al., 2016](#)). The SED modeling is not only an important tool to understand the jet physics but also constrain the extragalactic background light (EBL) that usually have an absorption imprint in VHE γ -ray spectra of blazars ([Abeysekara et al., 2019](#); [Finke et al., 2010](#)). The γ -ray studies of blazars are very important due to short variability times and to locate the blazar zone. The emission at high energy γ -rays is generally well correlated with lower energies, e.g., X-rays ([Aharonian et al., 2009](#)), the occasional orphan high energy flares can be hard to reconcile in one-zone model ([Aharonian et al., 2009](#); [Błażejowski et al., 2005](#)). The γ -ray variability can be used to discern the location of blazar emission zone (see, e.g., [Dotson et al., 2012](#)).

The interpretation of blazar SED is model dependant. The low energy bump of blazar SED is always the synchrotron emission of electrons in the jet, whereas the high energy emission (i.e., from X-rays to γ -rays) explained as inverse Compton (IC) emission of accelerated electrons in leptonic models (see [Marscher et al., 1985](#); [Sikora, 1994](#), for review). However the high energy emission can also be explained as the synchrotron

Figure 1.9 The light curve PKS 2155–304 above 200 GeV on MJD 53944. The data are binned in 1 minute intervals. The horizontal line represents $I > 200$ GeV observed from the Crab Nebula. The solid line represents the fit to the data. Taken from [Aharonian et al. \(2007\)](#).

emission of protons ([Mannheim, 1993](#)) in hadronic models or due to proton-photon interactions in lepto-hadronic models ([Böttcher et al., 2013](#); [Diltz et al., 2016](#); [Petropoulou et al., 2015](#)). Based on the value of synchrotron peak frequency ν_{sp} , the blazars can be categorized into three main classes ([Abdo et al., 2010a](#)). These blazar classes are following:

- Low Synchrotron Peak (LSP) with $\nu_{\text{sp}} < 10^{14}$ Hz
- Intermediate Synchrotron Peak (ISP) $10^{14} < \nu_{\text{sp}} < 10^{15}$ Hz
- High Synchrotron Peak (HSP) $\nu_{\text{sp}} > 10^{15}$ Hz

It is interesting that while almost all FSRQs are LSPs, the BL Lacs show a wide scatter in the synchrotron frequency and are classified as low frequency BL Lac (LBL), intermediate peak BL Lac (IBL), and high frequency BL Lac (HBL) ([Abdo et al., 2010a](#)). This suggests that the underlying physical conditions in FSRQs and BL Lacs could be different.

The most important observational feature of blazars is their dramatic variability. These sources very bright and highly variable at all wavelengths, however the variability is more pronounced at high energy ([Vercellone et al., 2011](#)). Blazars are usually variable on scale of months at radio frequencies to days at optical and high energies. The variability may be intrinsic to emitting particles in the jet or related to change of viewing angle. The γ -ray emission can be variable down to minutes time scale at γ -ray energy as shown in Figure 1.9. Due to variable nature of the non-thermal emission, especially at high energy, it is very important to monitor blazars (e.g., see [Böttcher et al., 2007](#)) to study the origin of variability. The time resolved SED modeling can be used to investigate the nature of underlying particle acceleration and radiation mechanisms ([Hu et al., 2020](#); [Yan et al.,](#)

Figure 1.10 A schematic representation of a shock wave propagating in a relativistic jet (left) and a three-stage evolution of the associated synchrotron outburst in the shock-in-jet model of Marscher et al. (1985). Taken from Türler (2011).

2016). Marscher (2016) presented a recent review of theoretical and observational models to explain the variability of the jets. The flare timescale is usually defined as the time taken by a source to reach the peak of flux from the quiescent state. Using the causality argument, the variability timescale Δt can be used to estimate the size of emission region R as

$$R \leq c \cdot \Delta t \frac{1}{1+z}. \quad (1.10)$$

Marscher (2016) provided a review of models of blazar variability.

The variability of blazar emission can be explained by a simple *shock-in-jet* model (Marscher et al., 1985; Marscher, 2016). The shock-in-jet model assumes a uniform expanding source in which particles are accelerated due to shock wave propagation, leading to synchrotron flares, as shown in Figure 1.10. Electrons are accelerated by the shock wave and lose energy by emitting nonthermal radiation and adiabatic losses while moving downstream of shock front. The emission evolves via a three-stage process as shown in Figure 1.10. The first stage is dominated by Compton emission, whereas the second and third stage is dominated by synchrotron and adiabatic losses, respectively. The self-absorption turnover constantly decreases in the evolution of flare, as shown by red curve in the right panel of Figure 1.10. The shock-in-jet model can naturally explain the blazar variability and particle acceleration in context of turbulence moving in the jet.

1.2.1 Superluminal Motion and Relativistic Beaming

Generally it is believed that the jet emission variability arises due to a shock propagating down the jet. The bright radio jets are important to study the jet kinematics and variability

Figure 1.11 43 GHz total (contours) intensity images of 3C 454.3 with convolving beam with $0.05 \times .05 \text{ mas}^2$ resolution at different epochs; top: 2009 January 24; bottom: 2007 November 1. Figure taken from [Jorstad et al. \(2010\)](#).

Figure 1.12 The superluminal motion in blazars as the jet blob moves from position A to B. Imported from [Ghisellini \(2013\)](#).

modelis in the AGN. The powerful radio jets usually show a core-jet structure as seen with the very long baseline interferometry (VLBI) technique. Figure 1.11 shows the high angular resolution pc scale radio jet structure of 3C 454.3 at two epochs ([Jorstad et al., 2010](#)). The radio jet shows a bright stationary core and moving radio knots. These moving knots produce optical and high energy flare via shock in the jet ([Jorstad et al., 2010](#)).

Usually these bright knots appear to move with apparent speed higher than the speed of light as seen in the radio maps ([Blandford et al., 1979](#); [Jorstad et al., 2005](#)). This phenomenon is called *superluminal motion*. The superluminal motion is a consequence the bulk relativistic flow at an angle close to the line of sight ([Rees, 1966](#)), as shown in Figure 1.12. When an emitting knot moves from point A to point B with a high speed $\beta_j = v/c$ in the source frame for time Δt_j traveling a distance $\beta_j c \Delta t_j$ at a small angle θ with our line of sight, the apparent speed of the jet knot in the lab frame β_{ja} becomes

$$\beta_{ja} = \frac{\beta_j \sin \theta}{1 - \beta_j \cos \theta}. \quad (1.11)$$

This is a consequence of different light arrival times as the source moves from point A to B. [Lister et al. \(2016\)](#) found that the radio and γ -ray emission of the jet is correlated and apparent jet speed β_{ja} , that peaks at $\sim 5c$, varies between $30c$ to $\sim 50c$ in case of bright sources. These high apparent speeds propose very small viewing angle θ .

Another important effect related to relativistic motion with a small angle is the beam-

ing effect. At small viewing angles ($\theta < 10^\circ$) the relativistic beaming effect of emitted radiation becomes important. The flux intensity is significantly boosted by the relativistic Doppler factor δ through transformations $I_\nu = I'_\nu \delta^3$, $I_\nu = I' \delta^4$ and $\nu = \nu' \delta$ from intrinsic to observational frames (Ghisellini, 2013; Rybicki et al., 1979), the primed quantity refers to values measured in jet co-moving frame. The parameter δ is called the Doppler boosting factor and given by

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1 - \beta_j \cos \theta)}, \quad (1.12)$$

where Γ is the jet Lorentz factor and $\beta_j = v/c$ is unitless speed of the jet. The $1/\Gamma$ represents the relativistic term, whereas the term $1/(1 - \beta_j \cos \theta)$ shows the conventional Doppler effect. For a viewing angle $\theta = 90^\circ$, we obtain $\delta = 1/\Gamma$. For $\theta = 0^\circ$ the Doppler factor becomes $\delta = \Gamma(1 + \beta_j)$. For a jet moving away, i.e., $\theta = 180^\circ$, the $\delta = 1/[\Gamma(1 + \beta_j)]$. In case of $\cos \theta = \beta_j$ (i.e., $\sin \theta = 1/\Gamma$), we get $\delta = \Gamma$.

A PL spectrum of source is Doppler boosted in the observer frame as $F_\nu = \delta^{3+\alpha} F'_\nu$. Due to relativistic motion of the emitting blob, the timescale of variability gets shorter as $\Delta t = \Delta t' / \delta$ and the frequency of photon is enhanced as $\nu = \delta \nu'$. The source size, given by Equation 1.10, now becomes

$$R \leq c \cdot \Delta t \frac{\delta}{1+z}. \quad (1.13)$$

Therefore for a given source size R at redshift z , the variability timescale only depends on δ . Typically $\Gamma \sim 10$ as obtained from radio jet kinematics (see, e.g., Lister et al., 2016). The correct determination of δ for a jetted AGN is very important to determine the source parameters in the jet frame. Moreover, the blazar samples are usually flux limited and the Doppler boosting effect may cause a selection bias. The study of γ -rays is particularly important to understand the origin of variable high energy emission. Böttcher (2019) discussed the recent progress made in the theoretical models of multiwavelength emission using γ -rays observations.

1.2.2 Blazar Sequence

A blazar SED can be typically characterized by two parameters, namely the peak frequency of synchrotron bump ν_{sp} and its peak luminosity $\nu_{\text{sp}} L_{\text{sp}}$. Studying the SEDs of a large sample of blazars, it has been found by Fossati et al. (1998) that the synchrotron frequency anti-correlates with peak luminosity. However Nieppola et al. (2008) and Fan et al. (2017) did not find the anti-correlation in the source frame SEDs and suggested that

Figure 1.13 The left panel shows the observed sequence of [Fossati et al. \(1998\)](#), whereas the right panel shows theoretical sequence by [Ghisellini et al. \(1998\)](#).

observed sequence may be a Doppler boosting effect. [Giommi et al. \(2012a\)](#) found that blazar sequence may be a selection effect due to flux limited samples. The more sensitive instruments in future may answer this puzzling question. [Ghisellini et al. \(1998\)](#) described this sequence due to radiative cooling of electrons in the jet which controls the synchrotron peak frequency and bolometric radiative power, as shown in Figure 1.13. The theoretical blazar sequence is physical in nature and independent of observed sequence. [Ghisellini et al. \(2008\)](#) suggested that a simple phenomenology, in which jet power and accretion processes are related, can account for luminous "blue" blazars and low luminosity "red" blazars. The right panel of Figure 1.13 shows a theoretical blazar sequence in which the electron peak energy γ_p is inversely related to u (jet ambient energy density), l_{inj} (the compactness of injected particles), l_{ext} (compactness of external seed photons) and L_{sp}/L_{sp} (ratio of luminosity of high energy to low energy component or Compton dominance). The radiative cooling mechanisms and their relevance in blazars and will be discussed in the details in next Chapter.

The radiation power of the jet is considered to be related to accretion power of the blazar. It has been found that bulk power of the jet constrained from the SED, is usually higher than the accretion power, suggesting that SMBHs might be spinning ([Chen, 2018](#); [Ghisellini et al., 2009b, 2014](#)) and the jets should be produced through BZ mechanism. [Böttcher et al. \(2002\)](#) proposed an evolutionary scenario in which the different SED subclasses can be described in terms of a reduction of the BH accretion power with time. [Ghisellini et al. \(2017\)](#) revised the blazar sequence with larger and complete flux limited samples and found that the sequence still holds for BL Lacs, while FSRQs show almost

Figure 1.14 The updated blazar sequence based on Fermi Third LAT AGN Catalog (3LAC) blazars [Ghisellini \(2016\)](#).

constant nu_{sp} for different luminosity bins. The updated version of blazar sequence based on luminosity bins of Fermi Third LAT AGN Catalog (3LAC) is shown in Figure 1.14. The colored shaded areas show the γ -ray luminosity bins and the solid lines represent related mean SED in each bin. Another important parameter of the blazar sequence is the *Compton dominance* (CD), which is the flux ratio of high energy to low energy component and which usually anti-correlates with ν_{sp} . The FSRQs still show a blazar sequence between ν_{sp} and CD ([Ghisellini et al., 2017](#)). The CD is an important parameter of blazar sequence since its independent of Doppler beaming and redshift ([Finke, 2013](#)) and its relevance in the blazar research will be discussed in Section 6.

Chapter 2 Radiative Processes in AGN Jets

This chapter mainly introduces the thermal and non-thermal radiation mechanisms in the relativistic jets which contribute to observed blazar SEDs. The non-thermal electrons refer to the conditions in which the radiative plasma is not in thermodynamic equilibrium. The intrinsic power of radiation at a frequency is given by luminosity, i.e., the rate of release of energy, as given by

$$L = \frac{dE}{dt}. \quad (2.1)$$

However, the radiation is usually measured by instruments as flux F , defined as energy passing through a surface of unit area in unit time ($\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), as given by

$$F = \frac{L}{4\pi d_L^2}, \quad (2.2)$$

where L is radiation luminosity and d_L is the luminosity distance. A better quantity is the spectral intensity I_ν , since the quantity I_ν/ν^3 is Lorentz invariant. Intensity is measured as energy released in a small band with spectral width $d\nu$ passing through a surface of a unit area in a unit time per unit solid angle. In case of blazars, the intrinsic intensity of the source frame I'_ν , becomes $I_\nu = I'_\nu \delta^3$ in the observer frame. The flux F and the intensity I are related as $F = \pi \theta_c^2 I$, where θ is the angular size of the source. Another quantity is the spectral emissivity j_ν , defined as radiation energy emitted by a unit volume in a unit time per unit solid angle. The radiation energy density u_r inside a source is given by

$$u_r \approx \frac{L}{4\pi R^2 c}. \quad (2.3)$$

2.1 Thermal Emission

In case of a thermal equilibrium, the particles in the plasma interact with each other and the spectrum can be described by a Maxwellian distribution ([Ghisellini, 2013](#)) given as

$$F(\nu)d\nu = 4\pi\nu^2 \left(\frac{m}{2\pi kT}\right)^{3/2} \exp^{-m\nu^2/2kT} d\nu, \quad (2.4)$$

where T is the temperature of plasma, m is the mass and ν is the speed of the particle. The thermal plasma is in thermal equilibrium and the its radiation can be approximated

by the Planck's function for blackbody radiation, as

$$B_\nu(T) = \frac{2h\nu^3}{c^2} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{h\nu}{kT}} - 1} \quad (2.5)$$

with the peak energy $h\nu_{\text{peak}} = 2.82kT_c$, where T_c here is called color temperature. Thermal emission goes as ν^3 , however at smaller energies ($h\nu \ll kT$) it reduces to ν^2 and called *Rayleigh Jeans law*, as given by

$$I_\nu(T) = \frac{2\nu^2}{c^2} kT_b \quad (2.6)$$

where T_b is called brightness temperature of the source. The integral of Planck's law yields the total flux of a thermal source and it gives the effective temperature of the blackbody, given by Stefan-Boltzmann's law, as

$$F = \sigma T_{\text{eff}}^4 \quad (2.7)$$

For a thermal source, the intensity I_ν can be approximated by the ratio of emission coefficient j_ν and absorption α_ν , called source function

$$S_\nu = \frac{j_\nu}{\alpha_\nu} \quad (2.8)$$

The intensity can be obtained by solving radiation transfer equation, as the radiation is absorbed or emitted along the radiation path, given by

$$\frac{dI_\nu}{d\tau_\nu} = -I_\nu + S_\nu \quad (2.9)$$

where $\tau_\nu = \alpha_\nu \cdot ds$ is the optical depth with absorption coefficient $\alpha_\nu = n \cdot \sigma_\nu$, with particle density n and σ_ν is the cross-section of particle-photon interactions. For a source of size R with $\tau_\nu \leq 1$, the optical thin emission follows

$$I_\nu = j_\nu R \quad (2.10)$$

When $\tau_\nu \gg 1$, the intensity follows

$$I_\nu = j_\nu \frac{R}{\tau_\nu} \quad (2.11)$$

This shows that the observed emission comes from the outer shell of the source with size R/τ_ν . When the particles are energetic and not in thermal equilibrium, then the mode of radiation losses are non-thermal. It is important to note that in non-thermal plasma,

the timescale of thermodynamic interactions are very long as compared to dynamic timescale of a particle. The most common form of a relativistic non-thermal electron distribution is a PL, given as,

$$N(\gamma)d\gamma = K\gamma^{-p}d\gamma. \quad (2.12)$$

Here N is the particle number density, $\gamma = E/mc^2$ is the unitless energy of the particle, K is a constant and p is the spectral index. Many astrophysical processes can lead to a PL electron distribution. For a relativistic electron with energy $E = \gamma mc^2$ the, any emission process would emit a photon of energy $h\nu < \gamma mc^2$. Therefore, the source electron energy involved in the radiative processes can be constrained by physical modeling of observed radiation, if the radiation mechanism is known. The main non-thermal radiation processes and the related particle acceleration mechanisms involved in blazar jets are discussed below.

2.2 Synchrotron Radiation

The equation of motion describing the kinematics of a particle in astrophysical conditions is given by

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\gamma m \mathbf{v}) = \frac{e}{c}(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}). \quad (2.13)$$

As the relativistic electrons of energy γ move in the ambient magnetic field B at an angle ψ , it spirals into a helical path and emit synchrotron radiation. The angular power of an electron is

$$P_s(\psi) = \frac{2}{3}r_0^2 c \beta_e^2 \gamma^2 B^2 \sin^2 \psi, \quad (2.14)$$

Figure 2.1 The synchrotron spectrum of a PL electron energy population inside a homogeneous source of size R .

where $\beta_e = v/c$ is unitless electron speed, $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \beta_e^2}$ is electron Lorentz factor, B is the magnetic field, and $r_0 = e^2/m_e c^2$ is classical electron radius. The total average power of an electron for a distribution of pitch angles P_s becomes

$$\bar{P}_s = \frac{4}{3} \sigma_T c \beta_e^2 \gamma^2 u_B. \quad (2.15)$$

Here $u_B = B^2/8\pi$ is the energy density in the magnetic field and σ_t is cross-section of Thomson scattering. For relativistic plasma, $\beta_e \simeq 1$. The gyration frequency of spiraling electron becomes

$$\nu_B = \frac{eB}{2\pi\gamma m_e c}, \quad (2.16)$$

where $\nu_L = eB/2\pi m_e c$ is the Larmor frequency of cyclotron case. The synchrotron cooling time of a particle at emitting at the rate P_s is

$$t_s = \frac{\gamma m_e c^2}{P_s} = \frac{7.75 \times 10^8}{B^2 \gamma} \quad (s), \quad (2.17)$$

suggesting that electrons cool rapidly in conditions with higher intensity of B , e.g., in BH magnetospheres where B is very high as compared to ISM. The synchrotron emission is highly beamed. The synchrotron frequency of a is the inverse of fraction of time of the orbit during which the synchrotron flash is observed. The observed synchrotron frequency is given by

$$\nu_s = \frac{3}{4} \frac{eB}{\pi m_e c^2} \gamma^2. \quad (2.18)$$

Interestingly for a pitch angle $\psi = 90^\circ$, the synchrotron frequency ν_s is higher than the Larmor frequency ν_L by a factor of γ^2 . Now, the spectral power of an electron $P_s(\gamma, \nu, \psi)$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} P(\nu, \gamma, \psi) &= \frac{\sqrt{3} e^3 B \sin \psi}{m_e c^2} F(\nu/\nu_0) \\ F(\nu/\nu_0) &= \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \int K_{5/3}(y) dy \\ \nu_0 &= \frac{3}{2} \nu_s \sin \psi \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

Here $K_{5/3}(y)$ is the modified Bessel function of order $5/3$. The function $F(\nu/\nu_0)$ has a peaks at frequency $\nu = 0.29\nu_0$. For any distribution of electron energies $N(\gamma)$, where $\gamma_{min} < \gamma < \gamma_{max}$, the coefficient of synchrotron emission j_ν becomes

$$j_\nu = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int P(\nu, \gamma) N(\gamma) d\gamma. \quad (2.20)$$

For a PL energy distribution of electrons (as given by Equation 2.12), the integral synchrotron radiation spectrum becomes

$$j_\nu \propto KB^{\frac{(p+1)}{2}} \nu^{-\frac{(p-1)}{2}}. \quad (2.21)$$

The most important feature of synchrotron emission is that a PL electron distribution yields an observed PL radiation spectra $j_\nu \propto \nu^{-\alpha}$, where

$$\alpha = \frac{p-1}{2} \quad (2.22)$$

is the spectral index. However, the synchrotron radiation is absorbed when the source is optically thick, i.e., $\tau_\nu = R\kappa_\nu > 1$, where κ_ν is the absorption coefficient. When the source is thick ($\tau_\nu \gg 1$), the thermal plasma approximation $h\nu \sim kT$ can be used to define the temperature T for frequency ν . Then assuming approximation that the electron absorbs the same frequency it emits and Rayleigh-Jeans regime ($h\nu \ll kT$), the spectrum of thick source becomes

$$I_\nu \propto \frac{\nu^{5/2}}{B^{1/2}}. \quad (2.23)$$

The spectra in thick regime is a $\nu^{5/2}$ PL and does not depend on electron spectral index p . Thus the synchrotron radiation of a PL EED in a thick source is essentially a double PL, that follows $\nu^{5/2}$ in thick regime and ν^α in thin regime, as shown in Figure 2.1. The absorption coefficient $\kappa_\nu = j_\nu/I_\nu$ can be given as

$$\kappa_\nu \propto KB^{\frac{p+2}{2}} \nu^{-\frac{(p+4)}{2}} \quad (2.24)$$

The transition from thick to thin regime ($\tau_\nu = 1$) happens at a turnover frequency $\nu_t =$, given by

$$\nu_t \propto [RKB^{(p+2)/2}]^{\frac{2}{(p+4)}}. \quad (2.25)$$

The ν_t is an important parameter in the study of radio sources as it can be considered to belong to both optically thick and thin regime, i.e., $\tau_\nu = R\kappa_\nu = 1$. Since protons are massive, they need strong values of magnetic field and particle energies which can put severe constraints on the acceleration models. However, in hadronic models, the secondary leptons contribute to the synchrotron emission.

2.3 Inverse Compton Emission

In the classical *Thomson scattering*, an electron is scattered of an electromagnetic wave and the differential cross-section of scattering is described as

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = r_0^2(1 + \cos^2 \theta), \quad (2.26)$$

where θ is the angle between incoming and scattered wave and $r_0 = e/m_e c^2$ is the classical electron radius. The total cross-section is given by integrating over the solid angle, and given by,

$$\sigma_T = \frac{8\pi}{3} r_0^2 \quad (2.27)$$

When the incoming photon have energy less energy in the electron rest frame than the energy of electron, the there is no almost no energy exchange and photon is deflected. When an electron is scattered to higher energy during interaction with a photon with relatively higher energy in the electron rest frame, the process is called *Compton scattering*. Consider the scattering between an electron at rest and an incoming photon, the energy of scattered photon by applying conservation of energy and momentum becomes

$$x = \frac{x_0}{1 + x_0(1 + \cos \theta)} \quad (2.28)$$

where $x_0 = h\nu_0/\gamma m_e c^2$ and $x = h\nu/\gamma m_e c^2$ is the unitless energy of incoming photon and scattered photon in electron rest frame and θ is the angle of scattering. For a simple case when $x_0 \ll 1$, there is no change of energy, i.e., $x \sim x_0$, as in the classical Thomson scattering. However in astrophysical conditions with non-thermal electrons, *inverse Compton scattering* is more relevant, in which a high energy electron upscatters the incoming photon. When incoming photon have comparable energy, then electron recoil becomes important. The differential Klein-Nishina cross-section as given by

$$\frac{d\sigma_{KN}}{d\Omega} = \frac{3}{16\pi} \frac{\sigma_T}{[1 + x(1 - \cos\theta)]^2} \left[x(1 - \cos\theta) + \frac{1}{1 + x(1 - \cos\theta)} + \cos\theta \right]. \quad (2.29)$$

Integrating the above equation over the entire solid angle, the Klein-Nishina cross-section becomes

$$\sigma_{KN} = \frac{3}{4} \sigma_T \left[\frac{1+x}{x^3} \left\{ \frac{2x(1+x)}{1+2x} - \ln(1+2x) \right\} + \frac{\ln(1+2x)}{2x} - \frac{1+3x}{(2+2x)^2} \right]. \quad (2.30)$$

When the electron is relativistic $\gamma \gg 1$, inverse Compton scattering upscatters the incoming the ambient photon. In Thomson regime ($\gamma x_0 \leq m_e c^2$), the incoming photon

of energy ϵ gains the energy about an order of γ^2 , i.e., the scattered photon has energy $x \sim \gamma^2 x$. This process can scatter the low energy photons to very high energies and electron cooling. In case of condition $\gamma x \gg m_e c^2$, the scattered photon energy becomes $x \sim \gamma$. The VHE emission is usually limited by Klein-Nishina cross-section. For relevance of these emission processes in blazar will be discussed in the next chapter. The IC frequency of electron of energy γ in Thomson regime becomes

$$\nu_c = \frac{4}{3} \gamma^2 \nu, \quad (2.31)$$

where the ν is the frequency of incoming seed photon. The average IC power of an electron is

$$\bar{P}_c = \frac{4}{3} \sigma_T c \beta_e^2 \gamma^2 u_r. \quad (2.32)$$

The lifetime of an electron at the energy loss rate P_c is given by

$$t_c = \frac{\gamma m_e c^2}{P_c} \sim \frac{m_e c}{\sigma_T \gamma u_r} \quad (2.33)$$

where u_r is radiation energy density. The u_r in a of spherical jet of size R emitting radiation at the rate L is given by

$$u_r \approx \frac{L}{4\pi R^2 c}. \quad (2.34)$$

When the synchrotron radiation provides the seed photons for IC scattering, the process is called *synchrotron self-Compton*(SSC). In SSC, the source seed photons are scattered by same electrons that produce them. The SSC emission is unavoidably always present in non-thermal compact synchrotron sources, for example in GRBs and AGN jets (see, e.g., [Finke et al., 2008](#), for SSC analysis of blazars). The ratio of synchrotron to IC power of an electron is given by

$$\frac{P_s}{P_c} = \frac{u_B}{u_r}. \quad (2.35)$$

This parameter might be important in study of astrophysical sources since it reveals the physical conditions inside the jet. In the efficient IC cooling, the cooling time of electron is smaller than the escape timescale R/c . The ratio of two timescales becomes

$$\frac{t_c}{(R/c)} = \frac{3\pi m_e c^3 R}{\gamma \sigma_T L} \quad (2.36)$$

where the dimensionless parameter $\sigma_T L / m_e c^3 R$ is called compactness parameter l , thus we have,

$$l = \frac{\sigma_T L}{m_e c^3 R}. \quad (2.37)$$

The compactness l is an important parameter of high energy sources. For $l \sim 1$, even the electron of low energy $\gamma = 3\pi \sim 10$ cool in a light crossing time, i.e., $t_c \sim R/c$.

The IC spectrum of a PL electron distribution $N(\gamma) = K\gamma^{-p}$ is can be given by emission coefficient

$$j_c(\nu_c) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{(4/3)^\alpha}{2} \sigma_T c K \frac{u_r}{\nu_0} \left(\frac{\nu_c}{\nu_0} \right)^{-\alpha} \quad (2.38)$$

where ν_0 is the seed photon frequency. The IC spectrum is also a PL similar to synchrotron emission and $\alpha = (p-1)/2$. In case of seed photon energy distribution $r_r(\nu)$, the emission coefficient can be obtained by solving the integral

$$j_c(\nu_c) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{(4/3)^\alpha}{2} \sigma_T c K \nu_c^{-\alpha} \int \frac{u_r(\nu)}{\nu} \nu^\alpha d\nu. \quad (2.39)$$

For SSC $u_r(\nu) \propto \nu^{-\alpha}$ and solution of the integral becomes

$$\int \frac{u_r(\nu)}{\nu} \nu^\alpha d\nu = \ln \frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\min}}. \quad (2.40)$$

Since the observed IC power is related to the seed photons density in the jet, depending on the distance of emission region from the BH, different sources can provide seed photons and the in such case the IC emission is referred as *external Compton (EC)*. As BH surroundings are dominated by different photon fields at various distance scales, the nature of seed photons can reveal the location of high energy emission region from the SMBH (Dotson et al., 2012; Yan et al., 2018). However this important issue is not yet settled due to various parameters in an IC model and poor angular and spectral resolution of current high energy instruments. The relevance of synchrotron and IC cooling processes in blazars will be discussed in Chapter 4.

Chapter 3 Particle Acceleration in AGN Jets

Since blazars are powerful γ -ray emitters and always bright on the sky, it is necessary that the particles in the jet must be relativistic and continuously energized by some sort of acceleration mechanism to compensate for the energy losses by radiation and other competing processes. The PL spectra of synchrotron sources also demands that the emitting particle distribution should be non-thermal. The supersonic outflow naturally produces shocks in the jet. In a *shock acceleration* scenario, the particles are accelerated at the shock front and diffuse downstream into radiation zone where radiative cooling takes place (see, e.g., [Kirk et al., 1998](#)). Consider a shock front moving with velocity $< c$ in a plasma jet. The particles move across the shock with upstream velocity u_1 and downstream velocity u_2 , as shown in Figure 3.1. For a particle of energy $E \simeq pc$, the fractional energy gain $\Delta E/E$ is the order of V/c , where V is the velocity of the downstream plasma with respect to the upstream plasma. The shock acceleration is a first order Fermi (Fermi I) acceleration and an efficient mechanism to produce relativistic particles in the jet.

Figure 3.1 The particle acceleration mechanism in astrophysical jets. The left panel shows the Fermi I, while right panel shows the Fermi II acceleration. The orange lines show bulk velocities and the particle trajectories are shown by red lines. Imported from ([Matthews et al., 2020](#)).

A second order Fermi (Fermi II) acceleration involves the energy gain due to scattering of particles by moving magnetic irregularities or magnetic mirrors repeatedly ([Fermi, 1949](#)). As the scatterer cloud approach moving with velocity u_c approach the particle, the particle undergoes a fractional energy gain or loss $\sim u_c/c$. Since the head-on collisions

are most likely, the energy gain is favored. For a relativistic particle, transforming from lab frame to cloud frame and back to lab frame, and integrating over the distribution of pitch angle, the average fractional gain becomes

$$\left\langle \frac{\Delta E}{E} \right\rangle = \frac{8}{3} \left(\frac{u_c}{c} \right)^2. \quad (3.1)$$

Since the index of fractional gain is 2 for moving magnetic clouds, the acceleration is called second order Fermi acceleration. Figure 3.1 shows the schematic diagram of Fermi acceleration mechanisms in the astrophysical jets.

Usually the spectra of accelerated particles in a diffusive shock acceleration is given by a negative PL as

$$N(> \gamma) = N_0 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{-s+1}, \quad (3.2)$$

with index s ,

$$s = \frac{\log p}{\log \varepsilon} + 1, \quad (3.3)$$

where γ_0 , p , and ε are injected energy, probability of acceleration and acceleration efficiency or gain, respectively. Usually both acceleration probability $p = N_i/N_{i-1}$ and energy gain $\varepsilon = \gamma_i/\gamma_{i-1}$ are assumed constant. The first and second order Fermi acceleration can explain the SED of blazars (Lewis et al., 2019).

3.1 Statistical Acceleration Scenario

The electron spectra can be curved than a simple power law. In a combined acceleration and cooling scenario, the curvature in the EED may not be merely arise as a result of cooling but due to acceleration mechanism if the energy gain of injected electrons is a function of the energy Massaro et al. (2004a). Such an acceleration is called energy dependent acceleration mechanism. In the many physical situations, the probability could be dependent on the energy itself. In a case, e.g., when probability p decreases with energy γ as

$$p_i = g/\gamma_i^q, \quad (3.4)$$

where p and q are positive constants. Massaro et al. (2004a) showed that in such cases, the integral EED can be given as

$$N(> \gamma) = N_0 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{-s+1-r \log(\gamma/\gamma_0)}. \quad (3.5)$$

In this case, an extra parameter r is induced in the electron spectrum $N(\gamma)$ which describes the curvature. In such an energy dependent mechanism, s and r are related to constants g and q , as

$$s = -\frac{\log(g/\gamma_0)}{\log \varepsilon} - \frac{q-2}{2} \quad (3.6)$$

$$r = \frac{q}{2 \log \varepsilon}. \quad (3.7)$$

Interestingly the curvature parameter r is inversely proportional to $\log \varepsilon$ in such description of acceleration, suggesting that a higher gain efficiency will lead to smaller curvature.

The nominal form of a log-parabolic spectrum is

$$N(\gamma) = N_0 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{-s-r \log(\gamma/\gamma_0)}. \quad (3.8)$$

The peak of such EED in $\log \gamma - \log \gamma^3 N(\gamma)$, becomes

$$\log \gamma_p = \log \gamma_0 + \frac{3-s}{2r}. \quad (3.9)$$

In energy dependent scenario, the gain ε is considered constant. However it may be possible that the gain fluctuates randomly in some physical process of stochastic nature (Tramacere et al., 2011). Assuming that particles are always accelerated ($p = 1$), a fluctuating gain can be described as

$$\varepsilon = \bar{\varepsilon} + \chi \quad (3.10)$$

where $\bar{\varepsilon}$ is the constant gain term and χ is random variable with normal distribution with zero mean value and variance σ_χ^2 . Note that ε is not random and varies in range $\varepsilon \geq 0$ with variance σ_ε . In such a setting, the particle energy after n steps is given by

$$\gamma_n = \gamma_0 \prod_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i. \quad (3.11)$$

Tramacere et al. (2011) showed that by applying the multiplicative case of central limit theorem, the differential energy distribution $n(\gamma) = dN(\gamma)/d\gamma$ is of the form,

$$n(\gamma) = \frac{N_0}{\gamma \sigma_\gamma \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left[-\frac{(\ln \gamma - \mu)^2}{2\sigma_\gamma^2} \right], \quad (3.12)$$

where σ_γ^2 and μ are

$$\sigma_\gamma^2 \approx n \left(\frac{\sigma_\varepsilon}{\bar{\varepsilon}} \right)^2 \quad \mu = \ln \gamma_0 + n \left[\ln \bar{\varepsilon} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sigma_\varepsilon}{\bar{\varepsilon}} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (3.13)$$

Such an EED resembles the log-parabolic law with the peak in the $\log \gamma - \log \gamma^3 n(\gamma)$ space as

$$\log \gamma_p = \log \gamma_0 + n \log \bar{\varepsilon} + \frac{3}{4r}, \quad (3.14)$$

where the curvature r is

$$r = \frac{\ln 10}{2n(\sigma_\varepsilon/\bar{\varepsilon})} \quad (3.15)$$

It is interesting that the curvature r of EED is inversely related to number of steps n and variance of gain term σ_ε . Thus a fluctuation of energy gain term also leads to a log-parabolic spectrum of particles. Therefore, in both energy dependent and fluctuating gain acceleration mechanisms, one expects an anti-correlation between curvature r and the peak energy γ_p as shown in equation 3.9 and 3.14.

3.2 Diffusive Shock Acceleration

The particle produced during the hot accretion inflow are injected into the jet supported by magnetic fields. The magnetized plasma in the jet is turbulent and the plasma oscillations are called magneto-hydrodynamic (MHD) waves. The acceleration of particles due to scattering by MHD waves is called stochastic acceleration, leading to the formation of the high-energy electron distribution (Becker et al., 2006) in a variety of astrophysical systems. The particles get energized as they bounce off the MHD wave. A stochastic acceleration mechanism is a second-order Fermi acceleration process and can be described as diffusion in the momentum space (see e.g., Katarzyński et al., 2006). The evolution of phase-space density of particles, f , is described by the momentum diffusion equation as given by

$$\frac{\partial f(p, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{p^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left[p^2 D(p, t) \frac{\partial f(p, t)}{\partial p} \right], \quad (3.16)$$

where $p = \beta_p \gamma$ is dimensionless momentum of particle, $D(p, t)$ the momentum diffusion coefficient. The particle number density is related to phase-space density as

$$N(p, t) = 4\pi p^2 f(p, t) \quad (3.17)$$

For ultra-relativistic particle, $p \simeq \gamma$ as $\beta_p \simeq 1$. Then the above equation becomes

$$\frac{\partial N(\gamma, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \gamma} \left[-A(\gamma, t) N(\gamma, t) + D(\gamma, t) \frac{\partial N(\gamma, t)}{\partial \gamma} \right] \quad (3.18)$$

with the momentum diffusion coefficient in Fermi-like acceleration process is a power-law as given by

$$D(\gamma, t) = \frac{\gamma^2}{2t_a}, \quad (3.19)$$

where t_a is the acceleration time of particle of energy γ . The acceleration term describing the acceleration efficiency is given by

$$A(\gamma, t) = \frac{2D(\gamma, t)}{\gamma}. \quad (3.20)$$

The given definition of diffusion leads to gain term

$$A(\gamma) = \frac{\gamma}{t_a}. \quad (3.21)$$

The acceleration time t_a is usually taken as a free parameter of the model. The kinetic equation including injection, acceleration, radiative cooling, and escape can be solved, yielding the electron energy spectrum $N(\gamma, t)$ at time t . The evolution of particles is dictated by the timescales of involved physical processes.

The equation governing temporal evolution of electrons in diffusive shock acceleration becomes

$$\frac{\partial N(\gamma, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \gamma} \left[\{C(\gamma, t) - A(\gamma, t)\} N(\gamma, t) + D(\gamma, t) \frac{\partial N(\gamma, t)}{\partial \gamma} \right] - E(\gamma, t) + Q(\gamma, t), \quad (3.22)$$

The $Q(\gamma, t)$ is the source term and $E(\gamma, t) = N(\gamma, t)/t_e$ the escape term with timescale $t_e \simeq R/c$ being escape timescale of the particles. The $C(\gamma, t)$ is the cooling parameter assuming synchrotron and IC losses, and given by

$$C(\gamma, t) = \frac{4\sigma_t}{3m_e c} \gamma^2 [u_B + u_r(\gamma, t)], \quad (3.23)$$

where u_B is the magnetic energy density of the jet and u_r is the photon energy density for IC cooling. The general form of stationery solution ($N(\gamma, t)/\partial t = 0$) for a simple cooling $C(\gamma) = C_0\gamma^2$ and no absorption is given by

$$N(\gamma) = m \exp \left[- \int \frac{C(\gamma') - A(\gamma)}{D(\gamma')} d\gamma' \right] \quad (3.24)$$

with m being the integration constant. The above definition of diffusion leads to ultra-relativistic Maxwellian of the form

$$N(\gamma) = m\gamma^2 \exp[-2C_0 t_a (\gamma - 1)], \quad (3.25)$$

which peaks at the energy defined by equilibrium energy, at which the cooling and acceleration timescales become equal, i.e., $t_c(\gamma_e) = t_a(\gamma_e)$, as given by

$$\gamma_e = \frac{1}{t_a C_0}. \quad (3.26)$$

In contrast to the fully deterministic acceleration, that lead to a mono-energetic distribution at equilibrium energy due to "pile-up", the stochastic acceleration leads to ultra-relativistic Maxwellian. Assuming PL relations for diffusion and cooling coefficient, $D = D_0 \gamma^a$ and $C = C_0 \gamma^b$, respectively, the stationary solution becomes a quasi-Maxwellian as given by

$$N(\gamma) = m\gamma^2 \exp \left[\frac{C_0 (\gamma^{b+1-a} - 1)}{D_0 (a - 1 - b)} \right], \quad (3.27)$$

that is a quasi-Maxwellian EED with the same power-law γ^2 and the exponential term, now, depending on the relationship between properties of cooling and diffusion terms. This shows that the competition between acceleration as diffusion process and cooling leads to a thermal or quasi-thermal energy distribution of electrons. This EED resembles the log-parabolic EED that arises in a statistical acceleration scenario (Massaro et al., 2004a), as shown in previous section.

Tramacere et al. (2011) presented diffusive shock acceleration scenario considering diffusion of particles due to interaction with magnetic turbulence. A turbulent magnetic field energizes the particles during the resonant interactions with MHD modes of the turbulence (Stawarz et al., 2008). The turbulence energy spectrum for magnetic field with ordered (B) and turbulent component (∂B), in terms of wave number $k = 2\pi/\lambda$, is described as

$$W(k) = \frac{\delta B(k)^2}{8\pi} \left(\frac{k}{k_0} \right)^{-q}, \quad (3.28)$$

with index $q = 1$ for Bohm diffusion, $q = 2$ for hard-sphere spectrum, $q = 5/3$ for Kolmogorov spectrum, and $q = 3/2$ for Kraichnan spectrum. The Diffusion coefficient $D(\gamma)$ is given as

$$D(\gamma) \simeq \beta_A^2 \left(\frac{\delta B}{B} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\rho_g}{\lambda_{\max}} \right)^{q-1} \frac{\gamma^2 c^2}{\rho_g c} \quad (3.29)$$

where $\beta_A = v_A/c$ is the Alfvén velocity in units of c and $\rho_g = \gamma c/eB$ is the Larmor radius λ_{\max} is the maximum wavelength of Alfvén waves. The parameter $\partial B^2/B^2$ is called turbulence level and related to the acceleration gain. A highly turbulent plasma would lead to higher energy gain due to frequent interactions. The acceleration timescale of particle

of energy γ , whose Larmor radii resonate with magnetic field turbulence length scale during the interaction, is given in terms of diffusion coefficient $D(\gamma)$ as

$$t_a \simeq \frac{\gamma^2}{D(\gamma)} = \frac{\rho_g(\gamma_0)}{c\beta_A^2} \left(\frac{B^2}{\delta B^2} \right) \Big|_{\gamma_0} \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{2-q}, \quad (3.30)$$

where γ_0 is the injected energy. Note that in the hard-sphere turbulence ($q = 2$), the acceleration timescale is independent of particle energy. A particle with higher Larmor radius becoming larger than the blob size would escape. The escape time for spatial diffusion $D_x \approx p^2 \beta_A^2 / D(\gamma)$ depends on size of the source as

$$t_e \simeq \frac{R^2}{D_x} \approx \frac{R^2}{(c\beta_A)^2 t_a}. \quad (3.31)$$

The coefficients of diffusion and acceleration terms in Equation 3.22 and the related timescales can be written as PL in terms of energy γ as

$$D(\gamma) = D_0 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^q, \quad t_D = \frac{1}{D_0} \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{2-q} \quad (3.32)$$

and

$$A(\gamma) = 2D_0 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{q-1}, \quad t_A = \frac{1}{2D_0} \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{2-q} \quad (3.33)$$

respectively, where the D_0 and A_0 have dimensions of inverse of time. A systematic acceleration term $S(\gamma)$ is given by

$$S(\gamma) = S_0 \gamma, \quad t_S = \frac{1}{S_0}. \quad (3.34)$$

It can be seen that the timescales depend on the turbulence index q and independent of energy for hard-sphere case ([Tramacere et al., 2011](#)).

For instantaneous mono-energetic injection, i.e., $N(\gamma, 0) = N_0 \delta(\gamma - \gamma_0)$ and no cooling losses and particle escape ([Kardashev, 1962](#)), the diffusion equation yields

$$N(\gamma, t) = \frac{N_0}{\gamma \sqrt{4\pi D_0 t}} \exp \left[-\frac{\{ \ln(\gamma/\gamma_0) - (S_0 - D_0)t \}^2}{4D_0 t} \right], \quad (3.35)$$

which is a log-parabolic distribution with curvature

$$r = \frac{C_e}{4D_0 t}, \quad (3.36)$$

where C_e is a constant. It is important to note that for hard-sphere turbulence ($q = 2$), the curvature r does not depend on the energy but the ratio of diffusion timescale t_D to evolution time t . The Equation 3.22 can be solved by making simple assumptions. [Cao](#)

Figure 3.2 MC simulation showing the evolution of injected EED at $\gamma_0 = 1$ for hard sphere (left panel) and Kolmogorov (right panel) turbulence. The dashed lines show a log-parabolic function in left panel and analytical solution (Becker et al., 2006) in the right panel. Imported from Tramacere et al. (2011).

Figure 3.3 The time evolution of curvature r of the EED in MC simulations of stochastic acceleration. The curvature for hard-sphere case (red line) is consistent with analytical solution (blue line). Imported from Tramacere et al. (2011).

et al. (2013b) numerically solved for $N(\gamma, t)$ assuming $t_a = t_e \sim R/c$ and $\lambda_{\max} \sim R$ for a turbulence level $\partial B^2/B^2 = 1$. For a continuous injection at low energy $\gamma \ll 2$, and accelerating the particles to an equilibrium energy γ_{eq} , i.e., $t_c(\gamma_{\text{eq}}) = t_a(\gamma_{\text{eq}})$, they found that resultant EED is curved and can reproduce the broadband SED or blazar Mrk 421 adequately well.

Tramacere et al. (2011) did detailed Monte-Carlo (MC) simulations to study the time evolution of injected electrons competing for radiative cooling and diffusive shock acceleration. They injected 10^5 particles at the lowest energy $\gamma_0 = 1$. The particle randomly undergo upscattering or downscattering. In each resonant interaction the energy dispersion of particle of energy $E = \gamma m_e c^2$ is $\Delta E \propto E^2 \beta_A^2 t$. In MC simulations, the time t plays the

Figure 3.4 *Left panels:* evolution of the particle spectrum with impulsive injection and no escape for the case of $R = 10^{15}$ cm and $q = 2$. Upper panels represent the temporal evolution of $n(\gamma)$; lower panels represent the temporal evolution of $\gamma^3 n(\gamma)$. Green solid lines represent the temporal evolution, for $B = 0.1$ G, with step of $0.8t_D$. The dashed and solid lines represent the case of synchrotron and SSC cooling, respectively. The vertical dot-dashed lines represent the equilibrium energy in the case of only synchrotron cooling. *Right panels:* evolution of the curvature as a function of t/t_{D0} . Upper panel shows the curvature r evaluated at γ_p , for the case of SSC cooling (solid lines) and for the case of only synchrotron cooling (dashed lines). The solid green line represents the prediction from Equation 3.36; lower panel is the same as in the upper panel, with curvature in r_{3p} evaluated at energy γ_{3p} . Adapted from [Tramacere et al. \(2011\)](#).

role of number of acceleration steps n in the statistical picture. [Tramacere et al. \(2011\)](#) found that the evolution of EED depends on the nature of turbulence spectrum, as shown in Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.3. The spectra are always represented by a log-parabolic function but the curvature falls consistently with $t \propto \gamma$ in the hard-sphere, as shown in Figure 3.3. This happens as the scattering timescale $t_{sc} \simeq D_x/c$ and the acceleration timescale $t_a = D_x/\beta_A^2 c$ does not depend of the energy.

However as cooling becomes important, the spectral curvature is affected as shown by Figure 3.4. As the cooling becomes important the curvature does not change with t or peak energy of parabola γ_p . The energy loss term synchrotron and IC cooling, corrected for Klein-Nishina (KN) effects, becomes

$$C(\gamma) = \dot{\gamma}_{\text{syn}} + \dot{\gamma}_{\text{IC}} = C_0 [u_B + K_{\text{KN}}(\gamma)], \quad (3.37)$$

where $C_0 = 4\sigma_t c/3m_e c^2$ is a constant of cooling term and $F_{\text{KN}}(\gamma)$ represents the convo-

lution of seed photon field and given by

$$K_{\text{KN}}(\gamma) = \int k_{\text{KN}}(4\kappa\epsilon_0)u(\epsilon_0)d\epsilon_0, \quad (3.38)$$

where $\epsilon_0 = h\nu/m_e c^2$ being the seed photon energy and u the seed energy density of IC cooling. The function $f_{\text{KN}}(\kappa)$, with $\kappa = 4\gamma\epsilon_0$, is approximated by [Moderski et al. \(2005\)](#) as

$$f_{\text{KN}}(\kappa) \simeq \begin{cases} (1 + \kappa)^{-3/2} & \kappa < 10^4 \text{ (Thomson limit)} \\ \frac{9}{2\kappa^2}(\ln \kappa - \frac{11}{6}) & \kappa > 10^4 \text{ (KN limit)}. \end{cases} \quad (3.39)$$

The function F_{KN} plays an important role depending on the value of κ and the seed energy density $u \propto B^2/R^2$ (SSC case). Figure 3.4 shows evolution of EED and curvature in combined scenario for the case of impulsive injection at $\gamma = 10$ in jet size $R = 10^{15}$ cm with no escape, assuming a hard-sphere turbulence ($q = 2$), for a magnetic field strength $B = 0.1$ G and $B = 1.0$ G. The electron energy at which the acceleration and cooling time scales ([Stawarz et al., 2008](#)) become equal is given by

$$\gamma_{\text{eq}} = \frac{1}{t_a C_0 [u_B + F_{\text{KN}}(\gamma)]}, \quad (3.40)$$

where t_a is the shortest timescale amongst t_D and t_A . For SSC cooling $\gamma_{\text{eq}} \propto R^2/t_a B^2 f_{\text{KN}}$, where for synchrotron case $\gamma_{\text{eq}} \propto 1/t_a B^2$. Figure 3.4 suggests that although a stochastic acceleration makes the EED curved, its evolution is significantly affected by the cooling. I study the relevance of combined cooling and acceleration scenario in Chapter 5.

Chapter 4 A One-zone Inverse Compton Model

Blazar emission can be described in terms of emission models. The emission can be either of leptonic or hadronic origin. [Böttcher \(2007\)](#) presented a review on leptonic, hadronic or hybrid models for emission in blazars. Typically the jet plasma is assumed to be electron-proton pair plasma, however positrons might be present via photon-photon annihilation. The leptonic models are generally favored over the hadronic ones as they can naturally explain the coordinated variability often seen in blazars ([Bonnoli et al., 2011](#)). A one-zone model is widely used in blazar SED modeling ([Chen, 2017](#); [Ghisellini et al., 2014](#)). A one-zone model assumes that bulk of the non-thermal emission of injected particles, as described in Chapter 2, is produced from a single spherical blob of radius R embedded in a homogeneous but tangled magnetic field B . Since the considered emitting region is always compact, its synchrotron self-absorption frequency is always large, therefore a one-zone model cannot account for the radio flux at observed frequencies smaller than a few hundreds GHz, which are produced by the superposition of several larger components ([Blandford et al., 1979](#); [Konigl, 1981](#)).

Usually the evolution of electron energy distribution in a non-thermal source depends on several competing mechanisms. The electron spectral evolution for a simple case of injection, cooling and escape is governed by the equation

$$\frac{\partial N(\gamma, t)}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \gamma} [\dot{\gamma} N(\gamma, t)] - \frac{N(\gamma, t)}{t_e} + Q(\gamma, t) \quad (4.1)$$

where the $\dot{\gamma} = \dot{\gamma}_s + \dot{\gamma}_c$ is the loss term due synchrotron and IC cooling, as given by

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{4\sigma_T}{3m_e c} \gamma^2 [u_B + u_r(\gamma, t)], \quad (4.2)$$

t_e is the particle escape timescale, and $Q(\gamma, t)$ is the source term. This equation becomes nonlinear especially in case of IC cooling and should be solved numerically ([Chiaberge et al., 1999](#)). As electrons evolve due to competing process the EED $N(\gamma, t)$ changes over time and such changes should be manifested by spectral changes in the emitted SED. A time-dependant modeling of blazars is important to investigate the underlying physical

Figure 4.1 The sketch illustrating the one-zone IC model. Relativistic electrons injected and accelerated in the jet produce radiation via synchrotron and IC processes. The different colors represent the source seed photons. Imported from [Romero et al. \(2017\)](#).

processes. However, the evolution of a physical parameter of the model can be also be studied by modeling the several epochs of a blazar with a steady model.

A steady one-zone synchrotron and IC model for the blazar SEDs is employed in this work, as shown in Figure 4.1. Depending upon the jet environment, different photon fields can provide the seed photons for IC scattering, however the case of SSC is worth studying as the SSC component is unavoidable. The model assumes a homogeneous spherical source of radius R with tangled uniform magnetic field B filled with an isotropic emitting electron energy distribution. For viewing angle θ , one has a Doppler beaming factor $\delta = [\Gamma(1 - \beta \cos \theta)]^{-1}$, which transforms frequency and luminosity from the jet frame to AGN frame as $\nu = \delta\nu'$ and $\nu L(\nu) = \delta^4\nu' L'(\nu')$, respectively, as described in Section 1.2.

Following the discussion in [Chen \(2018\)](#), $\delta \lesssim \Gamma$ has been adopted in our model calculations. The reasons for this choice is (in case of jet opening angle $\theta_j \sim \theta$) that the causality argument requires $\theta_j \Gamma \lesssim 1$ ([Clausen-Brown et al., 2013](#)), which is supported by simulations of axis-symmetric magnetically driven outflows ([Komissarov et al., 2009](#)). In

another aspect, the radio observation (e.g., [Jorstad et al., 2005](#); [Pushkarev et al., 2009](#)) and SSC process ([Nalewajko et al., 2014](#)) indicate $\theta_j \Gamma \gtrsim 0.1 - 0.7$. The synchrotron spectral luminosity of a thin source is given by

$$L_s(\nu') = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 \cdot 4\pi j_s(\nu'). \quad (4.3)$$

However the synchrotron emission, like thermal emission, might be self-absorbed depending on the source conditions. The emission coefficient of synchrotron radiation at frequency ν' are given by ([Blumenthal et al., 1970](#); [Rybicki et al., 1979](#))

$$j_s(\nu') = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int N(\gamma) P_s(\nu', \gamma) d\gamma \quad (4.4)$$

and the absorption coefficient is

$$k_s(\nu') = \frac{-1}{8\pi m_e \nu'^2} \int \gamma^2 P_s(\nu', \gamma) \frac{d}{d\gamma} \left(\frac{N(\gamma)}{\gamma^2} \right) d\gamma, \quad (4.5)$$

where $P_s(\nu', \gamma)$ refers the synchrotron power of a single electron and given as,

$$P_s(\nu', \gamma) = \frac{2\pi\sqrt{3}e^2\nu_L}{c} \frac{\nu'}{(3/2)\gamma^2\nu_L} \int_{\frac{\nu'}{(3/2)\gamma^2\nu_L}}^{+\infty} K_{5/3}(t) dt, \quad (4.6)$$

with the Larmor frequency $\nu_L = eB/2\pi m_e c$ and the modified Bessel function of order 5/3 $K_{5/3}(t)$. The IC emission coefficient is ([Blumenthal et al., 1970](#); [Rybicki et al., 1979](#))

$$j_c(\nu') = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int N(\gamma) P_c(\nu', \gamma) d\gamma, \quad (4.7)$$

where the IC power of an electron is

$$P_c(\nu', \gamma) = 8\pi r_0^2 c h \int f(\gamma, \nu_i, \nu') n_{ph}(\nu_i) d\nu_i, \quad (4.8)$$

with $r_0 = e^2/(m_e c^2)$ and $n_{ph}(\nu_i) = \bar{u}(\nu_i)/h\nu_i$ the seed photon number density. The function $f(\gamma, \nu_i, \nu')$ is given by [Blumenthal et al. \(1970\)](#),

$$f(\gamma, \nu_i, \nu') = \begin{cases} x \left[2q \ln q + 1 + q - 2q^2 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\Sigma q)^2}{1+\Sigma q} (1-q) \right] & 0 \leq q \leq 1 \\ 0 & else \end{cases} \quad (4.9)$$

where $x = \nu'/(4\gamma^2\nu_i)$, $q = E/[\Sigma(1-E)]$, $E = h\nu'/(m_e c^2)$, and $\Sigma = 4\gamma h\nu_i/(m_e c^2)$.

The intensity from a homogeneous and isotropic emission source should be angle θ_r dependent ([Chen, 2017](#)). The Figure 4.2 shows a sketch of such an emission region. The intensity at the sphere surface can be easily derived as,

$$I(\nu', \theta_r) = j(\nu') l \frac{1 - e^{-\tau_l}}{\tau_l}, \quad (4.10)$$

Figure 4.2 The intensity I is angle θ_r dependent in a homogeneous and isotropic source. Imported from [Chen \(2017\)](#).

where $j(\nu')$ is the emitting coefficient, $\tau_l = k(\nu')l$ is the optical depth, and $k(\nu')$ is the absorption coefficient. Note that the intensity is angle (θ_r) dependent. The total luminosity can be derived through integrating the angle-dependent intensity

$$L(\nu') = 2\pi^2 R^3 j(\nu') \frac{2\tau^2 - 1 + (2\tau + 1)e^{-2\tau}}{\tau^3}, \quad (4.11)$$

with optical depth $\tau = k(\nu')R$, the absorption coefficient $k(\nu')$ and the emitting coefficient $j(\nu')$ of radiation mechanism. For SSC, now, the seed photon energy density (i.e., synchrotron emission itself) at the center of the emission sphere may be different from that at the edge of the emission sphere due to light transport. At a distance r from the center, the synchrotron energy density is given by $u'_s(\nu', r) = \frac{1}{c} \oint I_{sy}(\nu', r, \theta_r) d\Omega$. Because of that the seed photons are dominated by optically thin emissions, one has an analytic solution of the photon energy density (assuming $\tau = 0$)

$$u'_s(\nu', r) = \frac{3}{4} \frac{L'_s(\nu')}{4\pi R^2 c} \left(2 + \frac{1 - r_*^2}{r_*} \ln \frac{1 + r_*}{1 - r_*} \right), \quad (4.12)$$

where $r_* = r/R$. However, the average value, $u'_s(\nu') = (9/4)L'_s(\nu')/(4\pi R^2 c)$, is used in this work.

For EC the seed photons dominantly come from either from the BLR or the dusty torus, depending on the location of energy dissipation R_{diss} from the BH, as shown in Figure 4.3. The radiation energy density in the jet rest frame, for jet with $R < R_{diss}$ is given by

$$u_{ec} = \frac{17\Gamma^2}{12} \frac{\eta L_d}{4\pi R^2 c}, \quad (4.13)$$

where R is the size of BLR or dusty torus. Outside an AGN component (i.e., BLR or torus) the radiation energy density decreases radially. [Ghisellini et al. \(2009a\)](#) discussed

Figure 4.3 A schematic representation of EC emission in blazar at a distance R_{diss} from the SMBH. Figure taken from [Ghisellini et al. \(2009a\)](#).

the case of seed photons from the accretion disk, BLR, dusty torus, and X-ray emitting corona. However, it has been shown that the γ -ray arise from a distance of ~ 1 pc from the BH, which can be considered as the interface between BLR and the extended torus. However the jet could be structured and the EC seed photons in the faster moving spine could come from a slow moving outer layer ([Chen, 2017](#); [Ghisellini et al., 2005](#)).

4.1 Physical Parameters of Model

The physical parameters of the a blazar jet are calculated from the SED observable quantities, i.e., the peak frequency and peak flux of synchrotron and the IC bump ([Tavecchio et al., 1998](#)). The lower limit on electron energy in a non-thermal source for radiation observed at frequency ν can be given as

$$\gamma > \frac{h\nu}{m_e c^2}. \quad (4.14)$$

The observed synchrotron frequency of the SED is given by

$$\nu_{sp} = \frac{4}{3} \gamma_p^2 \nu_L \frac{\delta}{(1+z)}, \quad (4.15)$$

The IC peak frequency ν_{cp} in Thomson regime is related to synchrotron frequency ν_s as

$$\nu_{cp} = \frac{4}{3} \gamma_p^2 \nu_{sp} \frac{\delta}{(1+z)}, \quad (4.16)$$

which leads to determination of γ_p as

$$\gamma_p = \sqrt{\frac{3\nu_{\text{cp}}}{4\nu_{\text{sp}}}}. \quad (4.17)$$

Combining above equations, we get

$$B\delta = \frac{\nu_{\text{sp}}^2}{3.7 \times 10^6 \nu_{\text{cp}}} (1+z). \quad (4.18)$$

This relationship relating peak frequencies can be used to calculate magnetic field B if δ is known. The source size R of the emitting region is constrained from the variability timescale Δt as

$$R \lesssim c\Delta t \frac{\delta}{(1+z)}. \quad (4.19)$$

The Compton dominance for SSC model is given by

$$\frac{L_{\text{cp}}}{L_{\text{sp}}} = \frac{u_B}{u_s} = \frac{4\pi R^2 c u_B \delta^4}{L_s}, \quad (4.20)$$

where u_B is the energy density of magnetic field, $u_s \sim L_s/4\pi R^2 c \delta^4$ synchrotron seed photons energy density with L_s total synchrotron luminosity, and L_{cp} the luminosity of SSC bump. From last two equations, we get the expression

$$B\delta^3 = \frac{2L_{\text{sp}}^2}{c^3 \Delta t^2 L_{\text{cp}}} (1+z) \quad (4.21)$$

Combining the above expression with Equation 4.18 and solving for δ and B , we get

$$\delta = 1.67 \times 10^4 \sqrt{\frac{\nu_{\text{cp}}}{\nu_{\text{sp}}^2 \Delta t}} \left(\frac{2L_{\text{sp},45}^2}{L_{\text{cp},45}} \right)^{1/4} \quad (4.22)$$

and

$$B = 2.14 \times 10^{-11} \frac{\nu_{\text{sp}}^3 \Delta t^{1/2}}{\nu_{\text{cp}}^{3/2}} \left(\frac{L_{\text{cp},45}}{L_{\text{sp},45}^2} \right)^{1/4}. \quad (4.23)$$

Thus, the physical jet parameters can be constrained by Equation 4.17, 4.19, 4.22 and 4.23. For EC dominated emission, the observed IC frequency ν_{ec} can be given as

$$\nu_{\text{ec}} = \frac{4}{3} \gamma_p^2 \Gamma \nu_{\text{ext}} \frac{\delta}{(1+z)}, \quad (4.24)$$

where ν_{ext} is external seed photon energy. The electron peak energy γ_p in EC is given by

$$\gamma_p = \sqrt{\frac{3\nu_{\text{ec}}}{4\Gamma\nu_{\text{ext}}}}, \quad (4.25)$$

whereas the magnetic field B becomes

$$B = 3.6 \times 10^8 \Gamma \frac{\nu_{\text{sp}} \nu_{\text{ext},15}}{\nu_{\text{ec}}}. \quad (4.26)$$

The seed photons energy density u_{ext} can be constrained by fitting the Fermi-LAT GeV observations (see, e.g., Kang, 2017).

Chapter 5 Evolution of Curvature in Fermi Blazars

On-wards from 1970s, many studies found that the spectra of blazars is significantly curved, even for single band observations (Odell et al., 1977; Rieke et al., 1974; Sitko et al., 1983). The multiwavelength spectral energy distribution (SED) shows more obvious curvature and spectra of some objects manifest significant breaks, when combining two or more bands emissions (from radio upto X-ray bands, e.g., Brodie et al., 1987; Ghisellini et al., 1986; Ledden et al., 1985, 1981). As mentioned in Section 2.2, a PL electron spectrum $N(\gamma) = K\gamma^{-p}$ would radiate a PL synchrotron spectrum $F_\nu \propto \nu^{-\alpha}$ with $\alpha = (p - 1)/2$ are related. A PL electron spectrum injected into blazar jet radiating synchrotron/IC radiation will become a broken power law (BPL) spectrum with spectral indices p and $p - 1$ before and after the break energy γ_b at which the cooling and escape timescales are equal. The change in electron spectral index $\Delta p = |p - p_1| = 1$ should manifest in the observed spectra as $\Delta\alpha = 0.5$. However, the broadband SED of blazars is significantly curved. Although a BPL spectrum can arise due to effect of radiative cooling on emitting electrons and can successfully fit the observed SEDs of many blazars, however such spectra are hard to obtain in a combined scenario of in which injection, acceleration, cooling and particle loss with different timescales. The physical process with smallest timescale would define the spectral shape $N(\gamma, t)$.

Figure 5.1 The log-parabolic fitting of BeppoSAX X-ray SED of Mrk 421 (left panel) by [Massaro et al. \(2004a\)](#) and Mrk 501 (right panel) by [Massaro et al. \(2004b\)](#).

The broadband blazar spectra is significantly curved, however [Massaro et al. \(2004a\)](#) showed that the spectra of Mrk 421 even in a small X-ray band deviates from a PL and that a log-parabolic law can adequately fitted the X-ray SED as compared to other models. The BeppoSAX wideband X-ray SED of two famous HBLs Mrk 421 and Mrk 501 is shown in Figure 5.1. The photon energy spectra of these blazars, $F(E)$ (ph. $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{KeV}^{-1}$), can be described by a curved PL of the form,

$$F(E) = K \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right)^{-\alpha + \beta \log(E/E_0)}, \quad (5.1)$$

where E_0 is the reference energy, K is a constant, α being spectral index and β is the curvature parameter of parabola. The photon spectral index Γ is energy dependent, $\Gamma(E) = \alpha + 2\beta \log(E/E_0)$, and the spectral peak is $E_p = E_0 10^{(2-\alpha)/2\beta}$. A log-parabolic spectrum is essentially a BPL broken with many breaks. A log-parabolic EED is given by

$$N(\gamma) = N_0 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{-a - b \log(\gamma/\gamma_0)}. \quad (5.2)$$

Such a spectrum can be easily generated in situations where the acceleration efficiency decays with particle energy or due to fluctuation of gain, as shown in Chapter 3.

Since curvature is an important parameter to not only characterize an SED but also provides insight into microphysics of blazar jets. This spectral form has one extra parameter than a power law but one lesser parameter than a BPL model which has four parameters. The fact that parameter β is the curvature about reference energy E_0 and its value depends on the energy range over which the model is fitted, the so called window effect, and, therefore, it is important to fit the such a function to the broadband synchrotron SED of a source especially when curvature is small. Usually E_0 is chosen as peak energy of the SED E_p . Therefore, the simultaneous wide band observations from instruments with good energy resolution is important to constrain the actual value of curvature. Interestingly, the synchrotron spectra from accelerated particle with a log-parabolic EED is also of the same form ([Massaro et al., 2006](#)), as

$$F_\nu \propto \left(\frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \right)^{-\alpha - \beta \log(\nu/\nu_0)} \quad (5.3)$$

Where the synchrotron observed spectral parameters α and β are related to that of emitting particle distribution, a and b , as

$$\alpha = \frac{a - 1}{2} \quad (5.4)$$

and

$$\beta \approx \frac{b}{5}, \quad (5.5)$$

where b is the curvature of emitting electron [Massaro et al. \(2006\)](#). Thus a curved electron distribution naturally gives rise to a curved synchrotron SED. The log-parabolic form for broadband SED component is

$$\log(\nu F_\nu) = \log(\nu_p F_{\nu_p}) - \beta(\log \nu - \log \nu_p)^2 \quad (5.6)$$

with SED peak flux

$$\nu_p F(\nu_p) = K E_0^2 10^{\frac{(2-\alpha)}{4\beta}} \quad (5.7)$$

and peak frequency

$$\nu_p = \nu_0 10^{10 \frac{(2-\alpha)}{2\beta}}. \quad (5.8)$$

The bolometric flux of the peaked component is given by

$$F_{\text{bol}} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi \ln 10}{\beta}} \nu_p F(\nu_p). \quad (5.9)$$

The electron curvature parameter b in a stochastic acceleration mechanism is expected to be anti-correlated to electron peak energy γ_p as shown in the Section 3.1 and 3.2. Furthermore, a positive relationship between α and β , which translates to a positive correlation between spectral parameters a and b , is expected. [Massaro et al. \(2006\)](#) successfully used a log-parabolic SSC model to fit the broadband SED of Mrk 501. [Massaro et al. \(2008\)](#) studied the curvature and spectral changes in 11 TeV BL Lacs observations from various X-ray instruments and found a bluer and broader when brighter trend in the SED, i.e., a positive correlation between peak energy E_p and L_p , while a negative correlation between E_p and β . These previous results suggested that the nature of particle acceleration in blazar jets is stochastic, however the evolution of curvature is not well studied in a combined cooling+acceleration scenario. Blazar spectra is significantly curved and usually show features at the GeV energy. It is expected that this curvature is related to an intrinsic curvature of EED as the γ -ray spectra usually do not show any signature of internal absorption or EBL attenuation in the GeV band ([Costamante, 2020](#); [Pacciani et al., 2014](#)).

In this work, the origin and evolution of electron curvature is investigated by inverse Compton modeling of quasi-simultaneous multiwavelength SEDs of Fermi bright blazars

Figure 5.2 Synchrotron peak frequency (as $\log \nu_{sy}$) vs curvature (as $1/b_{sy}$). The solid line gives the best linear fit relationship $1/b_{sy} = -(22.08 \pm 0.43) + (2.04 \pm 0.03) \log \nu_{sy}$ and dashed lines represent 1σ confidence level. The p shows the null probability of Pearson test. Imported from [Chen \(2014\)](#)

using log-parabolic IC model, as described in Chapter 4. There has been some previous efforts to study the signatures of an energy dependent or fluctuating gain acceleration mechanism in blazars. [Rani et al. \(2011\)](#) found the correlation between synchrotron SED curvature and its peak energy, which is signature of stochastic acceleration. [Chen \(2014\)](#) showed that the curvature parameter (in $1/\beta$) and synchrotron peak ν_{sp} of SED should show a linear relation in statistical acceleration scenario, as

$$\frac{1}{\beta} = A \cdot \log \nu_{sp} + B, \quad (5.10)$$

where the value of slope A depends on the nature of acceleration mechanism and B is a constant. For energy dependent mechanism $A = 5/2$, while $A = 10/3$ for random gain. [Chen \(2014\)](#) fitted broadband SEDs of 48 Fermi bright blazars and found a significant correlation between curvature and peak frequency with a slope $A \simeq 2$ roughly consistent with energy dependent acceleration, as shown in Figure 5.2. However the IC peak showed no such correlation which could be due to a complex distribution of ambient seed photons or transition between Thomson and Klein-Nishina regime.

[Xue et al. \(2016\)](#) used a second degree polynomial to fit a larger sample from Fermi 2LAC catalog and found significant correlation between curvature parameter and synchrotron peak frequency for both BL Lacs and FSRQs as shown in Figure 5.3. However they found that the slope for FSRQs deviate from the acceleration signature. However all the previous studies fitted the broadband SEDs with either a high degree polynomial or mathematical log-parabolic function to SEDs rather any physically motivated model-

Figure 5.3 Synchrotron peak frequency $\nu_{\text{peak}}^{\text{syn}}$ vs curvature parameter ($-1/c_{\text{syn}}$) for FSRQs (top panel) and BL Lacs (bottom panel). The solid lines give the best linear fit relationship $-1/c_{\text{syn}} = A(\log \nu_{\text{peak}}^{\text{syn}}) + B$. Adopted from [Xue et al. \(2016\)](#)

Figure 5.4 Synchrotron peak frequency vs synchrotron curvature ($1/b_{\text{syn}}$). The solid line is the best linear fit ($p = 2.958 \times 10^{-4}$) and the dashed red lines indicate 1σ confidence bands. Imported from [Tan et al. \(2020\)](#)

ing and, therefore, could not provide the details of the origin and evolution of electron curvature. Only [Ding et al. \(2017\)](#) fitted broadband SEDs with SSC model of TeV BL Lacs and found that the expected anti-correlation between curvature and peak frequency for these sources. [Tan et al. \(2020\)](#) fitted the broadband SEDs of 60 Fermi bright FSRQs with log-parabolic IC model and found that the expected correlation between curvature and synchrotron peak frequency, as shown in figure 5.4. They found that the slope of the relationship is consistent with an acceleration mechanism in which fractional energy gain is fluctuating, as explained in Section 3.1. Thus, an energy dependent or fluctuating gain mechanism may show the stochastic nature of acceleration mechanism in the AGN jets.

The SED from radio to UV or X-rays revealed a bump in $\log \nu$ - $\log \nu F_\nu$ representation. This component of broadband spectra is believed to be synchrotron emissions of accelerated electrons in the relativistic jet (see e.g., [Blandford et al., 1978](#); [Ghisellini et al., 1998, 1989](#); [Landau et al., 1986](#); [Sambruna et al., 1996](#); [Urry et al., 1995](#)). The high energy bump in the SED, from X-rays up to very high energy (VHE) γ -rays also mimics the same spectral properties of the synchrotron bump. Although a correlation between synchrotron peak frequency ($\nu_{\text{sp}} \sim B\gamma_p^2\delta$) and the SED curvature has already been found, it may not necessarily correspond to an intrinsic correlation between electron peak energy and EED curvature, since synchrotron peak shifts can also be caused by magnetic field B and Doppler factor δ changes other than electron peak energy γ_p . Physical modeling of simultaneous SEDs is important to check if the expected anti-correlation between curvature and peak energy of underlying EED truly holds, which means studying the evolution of intrinsic electron spectral curvature in blazar jets. Till now, only [Yan et al. \(2016\)](#) studied the evolution of curvature for a single source 3C 279 and found the source showed no signature of stochastic acceleration. However they poorly constrained synchrotron peaks due to lack of data and the sample is relatively small. Since blazars are extremely variable especially at high energy, i.e., from X-rays to TeV γ -rays, the simultaneous SEDs of a sample are important to study the evolution of curvature against the peak energy.

5.1 Log-parabolic IC Model

The broadband SED can be fitted with a one-zone IC model as described in Section 4 with a log-parabolic EED. A log-parabolic EED is employed, because of: 1), a diffusive acceleration mechanism can easily produce a log-parabolic EED as shown in Section 3.2;

2), the coefficient of second-order term measures the curvature, which is the parameter of interest in this study. Within an energy range from γ_{\min} to γ_{\max} , the EED follows,

$$N(\gamma) = N_0 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_p} \right)^{-3} 10^{-b \log(\gamma/\gamma_p)^2}, \quad (5.11)$$

where N_0 is particle energy density, γ_p is the electron peak energy, and b is the curvature parameter. With this form, electrons with energy $\gamma_p = \sqrt{\nu_{\text{cp}}/\nu_{\text{sp}}}$ emit photons at SED peak. The electron energy in the source EED ranges from $\gamma_{\min} = 2$ through peak energy γ_p up to a maximum energy $\gamma_{\max} = 10^4 \gamma_p$. The exact determination of γ_{\max} may be practically irrelevant as the losses are limited by Klein-Nishina cross section. The observed synchrotron SED is described as

$$\nu L(\nu) = 4\pi \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 \frac{\sigma_T c}{8\pi} u_B N_0 10^{-b \log(\gamma/\gamma_p)^2} \delta^4, \quad (5.12)$$

with $\nu_s = 4/3 \nu_L \gamma^2 \delta$ is the synchrotron frequency of electron of energy γ . The bolometric synchrotron power of the source becomes

$$L_s = \nu_{\text{sp}} L(\nu_{\text{sp}}) \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \cdot \ln 10}{b}}, \quad (5.13)$$

where

$$\nu_{\text{sp}} L(\nu_{\text{sp}}) = 4\pi \frac{16}{9} \pi R^3 \frac{\sigma_T c}{8\pi} u_B N_0 \gamma_p^3 \delta^4 \quad (5.14)$$

is the peak synchrotron luminosity. Then the SSC dominance in Thomson regime is given by

$$\frac{\nu_{\text{cp}} L(\nu_{\text{cp}})}{\nu_{\text{sp}} L(\nu_{\text{sp}})} = \frac{u_s}{u_B} = \frac{\sigma_T}{2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \cdot \ln 10}{b}} R N_0 \gamma_p^3, \quad (5.15)$$

where I have used the average synchrotron spectral energy density

$$u_s(\nu_s) = \frac{9}{4} \frac{L_s(\nu_s)}{4\pi R^2 c \delta^3}. \quad (5.16)$$

For external seed photons, the EC dominance becomes

$$\frac{\nu_{\text{cp}} L(\nu_{\text{cp}})}{\nu_{\text{sp}} L(\nu_{\text{sp}})} = \frac{u_{\text{ext}}}{u_B} \frac{17}{12} \Gamma^2. \quad (5.17)$$

Here u_s , u_B and u_{ext} are the energy density in synchrotron seed photons, magnetic field and external photons seed density, while u be the total ambient energy density in the jet.

The jet power of a component in AGN frame is calculated as

$$P_i \approx \pi R^2 \Gamma^2 \beta c u'_i, \quad (5.18)$$

where u'_i is the energy density of the i th-component in the jet frame. I calculate the magnetic P_B , electron power P_e , Proton power P_p (assuming $n_e/n_p = 1$), and the bulk jet power $P_j = P_B + P_e + P_p$. The radiation power P_r of the source is calculated as

$$P_r = \Gamma^2 \left(\frac{L_r}{\delta^4} \right), \quad (5.19)$$

where L_r is the total nonthermal radiation power.

Figure 5.5 The effect of SED variations in log-parabolic SSC model as the curvature increases from red ($b = 0.4$) towards blue ($b = 1$) line.

To understand the effect of curvature in the observed SEDs, the IC model curves generated by varying b from 0.4 to 1 are presented in Figure 5.5. While keeping all physical parameters same, merely a change in the electron curvature leads to a shifts in IC peak and Compton dominance. This shows that the IC peak is not necessarily associated to γ_p and spectral shifts can be associated curvature of EED. After the IC peak, the curvature changes are not very prominent due to Klein-Nishina effect and the SED curvature nearly corresponds to electron curvature. However, the effect is prominent in MeV-GeV band. In synchrotron bump, the curvature changes prominently from optical-UV to soft X-ray band. In IC bump, the changes are prominent in MeV-GeV band. Therefore curvature is an important parameter to characterize the spectral shifts in the SED. This suggests that curvature may be the third important parameter of blazar SED in addition to the peak frequency and peak luminosity.

For FSRQs and LSP BL Lacs, the EC becomes important as X-ray and γ -ray emission can be accounted with single emission mechanism (Shah et al., 2017). Recent works show that the emission region may be outside of BLR, and therefore the EC seed photons will

Figure 5.6 The comparison of dust and BLR components in EC model.

dominantly come from dust torus (see [Cao et al., 2013a](#); [Kang et al., 2014](#); [Yan et al., 2016](#)). The EC model assumes seed photons arising from a cold dusty torus emitting nearly as a blackbody with peak frequency $\nu_{\text{ext}} = 3 \times 10^{13}$ Hz. Only in few cases where the dust EC component alone fails to fit the high energy γ -ray emission, the contribution from $H\alpha$ seed photons from a thermal BLR centered at $\nu_{\text{ext}} = 2 \times 10^{15}$ Hz is included. The reverberation mapping ([Bentz et al., 2009](#); [Kaspi et al., 2005](#)) of BLR and dusty torus yields a constant seed photon density in AGN frame for all FSRQs. For example, the scaling relationship between disk luminosity L_d and size of BLR is $R_{\text{BLR}} \approx 10^{17} \sqrt{L_{d,45}}$ (cm). Assuming $L_{\text{BLR}} \sim 0.1L_d$, the BLR seed photon energy density $u_{\text{BLR}} \approx 2 \times 10^{-2}$ (erg cm^{-3}) is obtained. For dusty torus, the scaling relation $R_{\text{DT}} \approx 10^{18} \sqrt{L_{d,45}}$, assuming $L_{\text{DT}} \sim 0.5L_d$, gives the seed photon energy density $u_{\text{DT}} \approx 3 \times 10^{-4}$ (erg cm^{-3}).

The total external seed photons energy density $u_{\text{ext}} = u_{\text{BLR}} + u_{\text{DT}}$ is enhanced in the jet frame as $u'_{\text{ext}} \approx (17/12)\Gamma^2 u_{\text{ext}}$. The individual dust and BLR model components would obviously peak at different frequencies in the SED. The dust EC is compared with BLR EC model for same synchrotron parameters in the Figure 5.6. It is interesting that the EC spectrum in the keV-MeV band for dusty torus is steeper than that of BLR. This suggests that the observed hard X-ray spectral shape can distinguish the source of seed photons and, thus, can locate the site of high energy emission ([Cao et al., 2013a](#)). However it is important to note that SED modeling alone can not provide decisive conclusions about the γ -ray location as both components can adequately fit the γ -ray SED ([Hu et al., 2017](#)). The contribution of both BLR and torus seed photons may be important in blazars, since the γ -ray location is usually found to be at the edge of BLR. The external seed photon

energy density u_{ext} is left as a free parameter, constrained by fitting the Fermi-LAT GeV observations (Kang, 2017).

5.2 The Fermi Bright Blazar Sample

Since the blazar region size is usually constrained from variability timescales at high energy emission, in particular γ -rays, the model fitting at these energies is very important to constrain the source physical parameters (including curvature) and the location of emission region from the BH. The Large Area Telescope (LAT) onboard Fermi space observatory (Atwood et al., 2009) provide a unique opportunity to explore the extragalactic sky which is dominated by blazars. The LAT is a wide field of view and wide-band pair conversion detector which is sensitive to γ -rays in 0.1 – 300 GeV band. The energy of incident γ -ray can be calculated through energy of the pairs and the arrival direction constrains the position of the object in the sky. The Fermi is mainly a survey telescope and measures the sky every 3 hours. Figure 5.7 shows the schematic diagram of LAT. The high energy photon spectra is described usually by as PL function as

$$N(E) = N_0 E^{-\Gamma} \quad (5.20)$$

where Γ is the photon index. Then the observed spectra of the high energy source becomes $F_\nu \propto \nu^{-\alpha}$, where α and Γ are related as

$$\alpha = \Gamma - 1. \quad (5.21)$$

The first 4 months Fermi-LAT operations, from August to December 2008, provided the opportunity to study the AGN with unprecedented accuracy, the so called LAT Bright AGN Sample (LBAS) or 0LAC (Abdo et al., 2009). Abdo et al. (2010b) analyzed the first 6 months LAT spectra for LBAS catalog and found that the blazar spectra, especially in case of FSRQs, have a significant curvature and departs from a single PL as shown in Figure 5.8. Abdo et al. (2010a) compiled the quasi simultaneous SEDs of 48 LBAS blazars including the averaged data of first 4 months Fermi-LAT operation, Swift XRT and UVOT observations coincident with Fermi observing run. The broadband spectral data are also provided from many ground- or space-based and space-based observatories, including Effelsberg, OVRO, RATAN, GASPWEBT, Spitzer-MIPS and AGILE at longer wavelengths. This sample of blazars has been considered to model fit the spectra, similarly as in Chen (2014).

Figure 5.7 The Large Area Telescope schematic diagram. The telescope consists of an 4×4 array of 16 individual modules (Atwood et al., 2009).

Figure 5.8 The fitting of LAT spectra of four blazars with different models: PL (thin solid), BPL (thick solid), and log-parabola (dashed). Taken from Abdo et al. (2010b).

Figure 5.9 Definition of different LBAS blazar types based on the peak of the synchrotron component. Imported from Abdo et al. (2010a).

Based on the observed synchrotron peak, the sample is divided into three main classes, i.e., LSP, ISP and HSP, as shown in Figure 5.9. All FSRQs are LSPs while the BL Lacs are further characterized into LBLs, IBLs, and HBLs (Abdo et al., 2010a). Thus, in total, the whole sample consists of 23 FSRQs, 9 LBLs, 8 IBLs and 8 HBLs. Since the observed trends between SED parameters in a blazar sequence must be related to physical jet parameters, such a categorization gives us a complete sample to study the curvature and its relationship with other source parameters, mainly the electron peak energy. The LSP blazars (FSRQs and LBLs) make up 32 sources ($> 65\%$ of the sample) and the curvature properties of these sources are investigated for the first time in this study.

Since simultaneous data is not available at many frequencies around the synchrotron component peak in some LSP sources, the additional archival data from ASI data center (ASDC)¹ have been included in such cases. In some sources, integrated observations at 2 – 10 keV X-rays from Swift 1SWXRT catalog (D’Elia et al., 2013) are included to constrain the SSC component. For few sources with recently measured redshift, their values have been obtained from NED² data archive. Only for one source the redshift is not available and a value of $z = 0.4$ have been used in this case, similarly as in Abdo et al. (2010a). In many FSRQs the optical-UV data may be dominated by thermal big blue bump, so the UVOT data is used as upper limit for synchrotron emission. The red points in Figure 5.11 represent the quasi-simultaneous spectral data, while the grey and black ones represent other observations (see, Abdo et al., 2010a, for detail description) to guide the fitting. For some blazars, especially LSP sources, the data around the expected synchrotron peak is unavailable and may lead to poor estimation of peak value. However for each blazar, either synchrotron or IC components has a good coverage of SED, which makes the SED modeling less uncertain.

Compared to 0LAC, the number for blazars significantly increased (nearly 1600 sources at high galactic latitude) in its 3LAC based on 4 year integration. The photon index Γ of different blazar classes is different, declining from FSRQs towards HBLs through LBLs and IBLs, as shown in Figure 5.10. Although this can be explained due to peak shift, it suggest that the curvature of blazars classes may also be different. The curvature and peak energy of EED for 1392 blazars from the 3LAC sample have been compiled, for which the physical jet parameters of BL Lacs and FSRQs have been obtained using an

¹www.asdc.asi.it

²www.ned.ipac.caltech.edu

Figure 5.10 Photon index vs. synchrotron peak frequency of 3LAC blazars (Ackermann et al., 2015).

IC model (Chen, 2018). It is important to note that Chen (2018) derived the jet parameters of blazars from approximated IC peak frequency and luminosity, rather than fitting the broadband SEDs. Furthermore, Chen (2018) employed an SSC model for all BL Lacs, however, γ -ray emission of LBLs is usually needs an EC component (Yan et al., 2014). However, although the physical parameters for the 3LAC sample are not tightly constrained for individual sources, it may not significantly affect the statistical trends between the parameters due to large sample size.

5.3 SED Modeling and Results

The global physical parameters and curvature are constrained by fitting the SEDs. The variability timescales may be different in various sources (see Ulrich et al., 1997, for a review), Bonnoli et al. (2011) and Abdo et al. (2011) for the well-studied blazars 3C 454.3 and Mrk 421, and Nalewajko (2013) for a systematic study indicating a typical variability timescale in the source frame in the Fermi-LAT band of ~ 1 day; see also Gaur et al. (2010); Hu et al. (2014). For consistency, an average value $\Delta t \approx 1$ day (e.g., as Chen, 2018; Kang et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2015) is employed. For the injected electron distribution, each SED for a particular class of blazars, e.g., FSRQ, can be considered a different state of evolution of electrons and its its spectral curvature. The SSC emission is assumed in case of ISP and HSP sources, whereas the γ -ray emission in LSP cases is fitted as EC component. Similar to Ghisellini et al. (2015, 2014), the best model fits based on visual inspection for each source SED are presented in Figure 5.11 and the corresponding physical jet parameters are reported in Table 5.1. The broadband spectral parameters

Figure 5.11 The SED modeling of LBAS blazars. The simultaneous data are shown as red circles, while gray and black circles represent the historical and additional archival observations, respectively. The synchrotron, SSC, EC dust, EC BLR, and total model curves are represented by dashed, dotted, dashed-dotted, dashed-double dotted, and solid lines, respectively.

(peak frequency and luminosity of synchrotron and IC bump) and the calculated components of jet power are reported in Table 5.2. The red points in Figure 5.11 represent the quasi-simultaneous spectral data, while the gray and black ones represent historical observations (see [Abdo et al., 2010a](#), for a detailed description) to guide our fitting. It can be seen that, for all blazars, either the synchrotron or IC component has a good coverage of SED data, which makes the modeling less uncertain. While the sample is limited due to availability of simultaneous observations of blazars, the meaningful statistical trends can highlight the relationship between curvature and source physical parameters. The error bars of the physical parameters b and γ_p are obtained using the average of uncertainties in the SED peak frequency and an average SED curvature (see Table 1 of [Chen, 2014](#)).

I find that SSC emission can successfully reproduce the whole SED of IBLs and HBLs (SSC blazars), which is consistent with previous studies (e.g., [Yan et al., 2014](#); [Zhang](#)

Figure 5.11 — continued.

et al., 2012, and references therein), while the γ -rays in FSRQs and LBLs (EC blazars) necessarily need an EC component to explain their GeV spectra (e.g., see Yan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2013). In some EC blazars the VHE γ -rays in the LAT band necessarily need a BLR component, suggesting that the γ -ray region in some blazars may be at the edge of BLR. In a few HSP sources, for example J1104.5+3811, when multiple X-ray observations are available, the low state spectra are fitted conforming to our steady state model. The external seed photons in some sources is lower than the expected constant value in the jet frame. This suggests that many blazars do not follow the reverberation mapping scaling relationship or the BLR and dusty torus may have different value of covering factor in different sources.

5.3.1 Physical Parameters Distributions

Figure 5.12 presents the distribution of the modeling parameters corresponding to best model fits presented in Figure 5.11. It can be seen that the parameters corresponding to FSRQs and BL Lac classes occupy different parameter space, especially for Doppler factor

Figure 5.11 — continued.

δ , electron peak energy γ_p and the electron curvature b . On average, the δ for FSRQs is the largest among all classes. While magnetic field B varies in the range $\sim 0.02 - 1$ G, the EC blazars, on average, have higher magnetic field (< 0.2 G) as compared to SSC ones (> 0.2 G). The peak energy γ_p systematically increases from low to high synchrotron peaked blazars. While γ_p for EC blazars remains in the range $\sim 400 - 5000$, its value for SSC dominated blazars varies in a significantly large range ($\sim 5000 - 160,000$). This shows that the synchrotron peak frequency shifts in EC blazars are mainly dominated by cooling due to a higher B and δ , which increases the total ambient energy density in the jet u' , whereas the peak shifts in SSC sources are caused by γ_p . Interestingly, the curvature b decreases systematically from FSRQs toward HBLs.

Figure 5.13 shows that jet power P_j and the electron peak energy γ_p show a strong inverse relationship $\log P_j \approx -1.3 \log \gamma_p + 50.5$, that is a signature of blazar sequence (Ghisellini et al., 1998). On the other hand, jet power and the curvature are positively related through the best linear relationship $b \approx 0.06 \log P_j - 2.2$ (see right panel of Figure

Figure 5.11 — continued.

5.13). Thus, the curvature reveals the physical jet conditions and might be considered an important parameter of blazar sequence. Our model parameter distributions and their average values are consistent with others studies (Chen, 2018; Ghisellini et al., 2015, 2014; Yan et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2013) and, therefore, justifies the physical relationship of b and γ_p , which changes drastically from EC to SSC cases.

5.3.2 The Curvature vs. Peak Energy

I study the relationship between spectral curvature b and peak energy of EED γ_p , shown in Figure 5.14, suggesting that the curvature in FSRQs and BL Lacs evolves differently. The LBAS blazars show an anti-correlation between γ_p and b for of BL Lacs. The best linear fit to BL Lacs (blue line in Figure 5.14) yields a relationship $b \simeq -0.16 \log \gamma_p + 1.24$ and the Pearson test suggests a significant anti-correlation with coefficient $\rho \simeq -0.7$ and a chance probability $P \simeq 10^{-4}$. The FSRQs dominate at low γ_p and deviate from the BL Lacs. FSRQs show a positive linear relationship $b \simeq 0.2 \log \gamma_p + 0.17$ (see the red line in Figure 5.14); however the correlation is not strong ($\rho \simeq 0.3$ and $P \simeq 0.14$).

Figure 5.12 Distributions of physical jet parameters of the blazar sample.

Figure 5.13 The relationship of jet power P_j with electron peak energy γ_p (left) and curvature parameter b (right). The solid lines represent the bisector linear fit.

Figure 5.14 Relationship between curvature parameter b and electron break energy γ_p for blazars. The colored points and lines show the FSRQs and BL Lacs in the LBAS sample and the best linear fit, while the green line shows the sample mean error bar. The black dots and line show the parameters and corresponding best linear fit to the 3LAC blazar sample from [Chen \(2018\)](#).

The 3LAC sample also shows an inverse relationship between curvature and peak energy with a similar slope ($= -0.17$) as in case of LBAS BL Lacs; however the correlation is not strong due to large scatter at low γ_p . This may be due to significant overlap at low energies between FSRQs and BL Lacs, as revealed in our exact modeling of LBAS blazars, suggesting that the curvature evolves differently against γ_p in FSRQs as compared to BL Lacs.

Figure 5.15 Relationship between curvature parameter b and electron break energy γ_p for TeV BL Lacs. The solid line shows the best linear fit.

I also compare our results with [Ding et al. \(2017\)](#), who fitted the sample of 29 TeV BL Lacs having low and high states based on 1 TeV observations with a log-parabolic SSC model and found negative correlation between curvature and synchrotron peak frequency. It is found that the curvature and peak energy of EED derived from their model parameters

(see Table 2 in [Ding et al., 2017](#)) follows a strong inverse relationship $r \simeq -0.6 \log \gamma_p + 3.43$ with $\rho \simeq -0.54$ and $P \sim 10^{-4}$, where $r = b$ and $\gamma_p = \gamma_0 \exp[(3 - s)/2r]$. Since FSRQs in our sample do not show the signature of acceleration, I suggest that the anti-correlation between synchrotron peak frequency and SED curvature found by [Chen \(2014\)](#) does not translate to an intrinsic inverse relationship between γ_p and b for all types of blazars, but only for BL Lacs.

BL Lacs:

The log-parabolic nature of EED and the negative correlation found in BL Lacs can be explained in a stochastic acceleration, as mentioned in Section 3.1 and 3.2. Solving kinetic equation for a mono-energetic injection and diffusion in momentum space which is described as a stochastic process, [Tramacere et al. \(2011\)](#) and [Chen \(2014\)](#) showed that the EED at time t can be approximated by log-parabolic form and its curvature r is related to the diffusion coefficient $D(\gamma, t) = D_0(\gamma/\gamma_0)^q$, as

$$r \propto \frac{1}{D_0 t} \quad (5.22)$$

where q is the index of magnetic turbulence spectrum, as explained in Section 3.2. The curvature decreases continuously during the acceleration process, especially in case of $q = 2$ (hard-sphere approximation). Therefore, in both acceleration mechanisms, one expects an anti-correlation between electron peak energy and curvature of EED as shown by BL Lacs. The hard-sphere acceleration with a constant injection and diffusion coefficient in a conical jet can reproduce the SEDs of a blazar adequately well ([Asano et al., 2018](#)).

FSRQs:

A mild positive relationship between b and γ_p for FSRQs can be explained by strong cooling during the spectral evolution of injected electron population. Figure 5.14 shows that curvature of log-parabolic EED, in typical conditions of an FSRQ, would evolve in a regime where a dominant radiative cooling completely compensates the acceleration and the curvature either rises mildly and reaches nearly a steady value, as predicted by [Tramacere et al. \(2011\)](#). This happens as the cooling timescale at the peak energy $t_c(\gamma_p) = 3mc/4\sigma_T \gamma_p u'$ becomes nearly equal to the typical acceleration timescale $t_a(\gamma_p)$ in the evolution of injected particle spectra. When cooling becomes relevant, it should restrict the growth of γ_p as seed photon energy density would increase ([Ghisellini et al., 1998](#)). The γ_p for FSRQs in our sample indeed vary within a very narrow range.

Figure 5.16 The relationship between the total ambient jet energy density u' and curvature parameter b and for FSRQs (left) and BL Lacs (right).

The strong cooling in FSRQs is manifested by the fact that total ambient energy density in the jet $u' = u'_B + u'_s + u'_{\text{ext}}$ is larger in FSRQs than that in BL Lacs, due to higher magnetic field B and an additional EC component with u'_{ext} . Yan et al. (2016) also studied the relationship between the peak energy of log-parabolic EED and its curvature by modeling 14 SEDs of 3C 279 representing different epochs, and found a positive correlation between them. However, their results might be ambiguous due to poorly constrained γ_p due to a lack of data around synchrotron peak (see their Fig. 1). Nevertheless, our modeling confirms that the log-parabolic EED in FSRQs evolves within a cooling dominated regime where its curvature grows mildly with γ_p or remains almost steady. The u' and b , for FSRQs, are positively related as $b = 0.1 \log u' + 0.97$ with a mild correlation ($\rho = 0.37$ and $P \sim 8 \times 10^{-2}$) as opposed to BL Lacs which show a shallower relation $b = 0.03 \log u' + 0.71$ with slope = 0.03 and negligible correlation, as shown in Figure 5.16.

However it is worth mentioning that due to a lack of stochastic acceleration signature in FSRQs, the true nature of particle acceleration in these sources remains hidden. The value of dust seed photon external density required for some sources is lower than expected constant value ($\sim 10^{-4} \text{ erg cm}^{-3}$) obtained from reverberation mapping. Similarly the BLR seed photon energy density is significantly lower the expected value ($\sim 10^{-2} \text{ erg cm}^{-3}$). It could be related to a different covering factor η for blazars or the γ -ray location may be at pc scale from the SMBH. However, the significant contribution of BLR component suggests that the location may be at the edge of BLR at sub-pc scale.

Table 5.1 Physical Parameters of LBAS Blazars.

Name (OFGL)	z	Type	SED	B	Log R	δ	γ_p	b	u'
J0033.6-1921	0.610	BLLAC	HSP	0.06	6.55E+16	25	37803	0.51	3.86E-06
J0050.5-0928	0.635	BLLAC	ISP	0.13	5.65E+16	22	4870	0.60	1.71E-05
J0137.1+4751	0.859	FSRQ	LSP	0.02	1.08E+17	42	20775	0.66	4.31E-07
J0210.8-5100	1.003	FSRQ	LSP	0.21	4.24E+16	16	16886	0.75	4.60E-05
J0222.6+4302	0.444	BLLAC	ISP	0.11	5.12E+16	20	57880	0.42	1.32E-05
J0229.5-3640	2.115	FSRQ	LSP	0.34	5.19E+16	20	5788	0.65	1.17E-04
J0238.4+2855	1.213	FSRQ	LSP	0.33	3.02E+16	12	43404	0.50	1.09E-04
J0238.6+1636	0.940	BLLAC	LSP	2.84	1.30E+16	5	4870	0.57	8.19E-03
J0349.8-2102	2.944	FSRQ	LSP	0.04	5.03E+16	19	129578	0.55	1.36E-06
J0423.1-0112	0.915	FSRQ	LSP	0.06	4.15E+16	16	25854	0.47	4.00E-06
J0428.7-3755	1.112	BLLAC	LSP	0.20	5.70E+16	22	6879	0.71	4.24E-05
J0449.7-4348	0.205	BLLAC	HSP	0.01	5.92E+16	23	18303	0.75	1.36E-07
J0457.1-2325	1.003	FSRQ	LSP	0.08	2.80E+16	11	163129	0.43	6.96E-06
J0507.9+6739	0.416	BLLAC	HSP	0.38	1.95E+16	8	115486	0.51	1.43E-04
J0516.2-6200	1.300	BLLAC	LSP	0.21	4.48E+16	17	20537	0.56	4.33E-05
J0531.0+1331	2.070	FSRQ	LSP	2.01	1.64E+16	6	2304	0.70	4.08E-03
J0538.8-4403	0.892	BLLAC	LSP	0.75	5.27E+16	20	1252	1.00	1.97E-02
J0712.9+5034	0.400	BLLAC	LSP	0.17	8.42E+16	33	861	0.71	4.01E-03
J0722.0+7120	0.310	BLLAC	ISP	0.47	5.65E+16	22	1252	1.20	5.42E-02
J0730.4-1142	1.589	FSRQ	LSP	0.36	7.16E+16	28	516	0.75	1.45E-02
J0855.4+2009	0.306	BLLAC	LSP	0.08	1.28E+17	49	1296	0.82	9.29E-04
J0921.2+4437	2.190	FSRQ	LSP	0.88	8.54E+16	33	746	0.96	1.24E-01
J1015.2+4927	0.212	BLLAC	HSP	0.46	6.33E+16	24	613	0.88	1.29E-02
J1057.8+0138	0.888	BLLAC	LSP	0.06	1.05E+17	41	1728	0.57	1.39E-03
J1058.9+5629	0.143	BLLAC	ISP	0.11	8.85E+16	34	1103	0.63	4.43E-03
J1104.5+3811	0.030	BLLAC	HSP	0.16	7.76E+16	30	781	0.75	5.77E-03
J1159.2+2912	0.729	FSRQ	LSP	0.48	8.15E+16	31	410	0.70	9.40E-02
J1221.7+2814	0.102	BLLAC	ISP	0.20	7.55E+16	29	1505	0.68	3.22E-03
J1229.1+0202	0.158	FSRQ	LSP	0.26	4.52E+16	17	2304	0.71	2.32E-03
J1248.7+5811	0.847	BLLAC	ISP	0.12	1.02E+17	39	559	0.76	5.84E-03
J1256.1-0548	0.536	FSRQ	LSP	0.50	5.24E+16	20	1053	0.83	1.57E-03
J1310.6+3220	0.997	FSRQ	LSP	0.13	9.05E+16	35	917	0.80	3.03E-03
J1457.6-3538	1.424	FSRQ	LSP	0.14	8.14E+16	31	994	0.71	9.06E-04
J1504.4+1030	1.839	FSRQ	LSP	0.57	5.81E+16	22	613	0.96	1.91E-02
J1512.7-0905	0.360	FSRQ	LSP	0.76	2.93E+16	11	950	1.00	1.46E-02
J1522.2+3143	1.487	FSRQ	LSP	0.27	8.14E+16	31	400	0.59	3.57E-03
J1543.1+6130	0.117	BLLAC	ISP	0.41	7.95E+16	31	487	0.90	1.25E-02
J1653.9+3946	0.033	BLLAC	HSP	0.12	6.88E+16	27	1326	0.75	8.57E-03
J1719.3+1746	0.137	BLLAC	LSP	0.07	1.03E+17	40	1479	0.82	4.80E-03
J1751.5+0935	0.322	BLLAC	LSP	0.32	4.24E+16	16	876	0.90	3.05E-02
J1849.4+6706	0.657	FSRQ	LSP	0.18	5.93E+16	23	972	0.82	5.96E-02
J2000.2+6506	0.047	BLLAC	HSP	0.02	5.16E+16	20	5464	0.52	6.02E-05
J2143.2+1741	0.213	FSRQ	LSP	0.20	6.05E+16	23	566	0.63	3.51E-03
J2158.8-3014	0.116	BLLAC	HSP	0.21	6.26E+16	24	917	0.76	6.62E-03
J2202.4+4217	0.069	BLLAC	ISP	0.83	3.45E+16	13	876	0.62	2.02E-02
J2254.0+1609	0.859	FSRQ	LSP	0.42	9.75E+16	38	410	0.88	2.15E-02
J2327.3+0947	1.843	FSRQ	LSP	0.49	7.86E+16	30	415	0.65	1.05E-01
J2345.5-1559	0.621	FSRQ	LSP	0.40	4.69E+16	18	907	0.85	3.73E-02

Table 5.2 Spectral Parameters and Jet Powers of LBAS Blazars.

Name (OFGL)	Type	SED	P_B	P_c	P_p	P_j	P_r	v_{sp}	$v_{sp}L_{sp}$	v_{cp}	$v_{cp}L_{cp}$
J0033.6-1921	BLLAC	HSP	3.91E+43	7.73E+44	1.11E+45	1.92E+45	2.76E+44	6.31E+15	1.08E+46	3.98E+24	1.24E+46
J0050.5-0928	BLLAC	ISP	9.64E+43	4.50E+45	3.02E+46	3.48E+46	1.63E+45	2.51E+14	2.94E+46	1.00E+22	5.92E+46
J0137.1+4751	FSRQ	LSP	2.42E+45	9.90E+44	8.17E+45	1.16E+46	2.80E+45	1.00E+14	8.14E+46	1.58E+23	9.37E+46
J0210.8-5100	FSRQ	LSP	7.78E+44	5.64E+45	1.37E+47	1.43E+47	2.84E+45	1.58E+13	4.40E+46	3.98E+22	4.21E+47
J0222.6+4302	BLLAC	ISP	3.19E+43	5.56E+45	6.72E+45	1.23E+46	3.62E+44	1.00E+15	3.05E+46	1.00E+24	5.03E+46
J0229.5-3640	FSRQ	LSP	1.27E+45	2.21E+45	1.37E+46	1.72E+46	2.03E+46	6.31E+13	1.06E+47	3.98E+22	1.71E+48
J0238.4+2855	FSRQ	LSP	1.95E+45	2.98E+45	1.06E+47	1.11E+47	3.05E+45	1.00E+13	4.39E+46	1.00E+22	3.21E+47
J0238.6+1636	BLLAC	LSP	9.89E+44	9.40E+45	1.09E+47	1.20E+47	2.62E+45	2.51E+13	1.09E+47	2.51E+23	9.75E+47
J0349.8-2102	FSRQ	LSP	2.31E+46	1.55E+45	2.31E+46	4.77E+46	2.61E+46	6.31E+13	4.30E+47	3.98E+22	4.57E+48
J0423.1-0112	FSRQ	LSP	1.92E+45	2.44E+45	5.21E+46	5.65E+46	2.54E+45	1.58E+13	5.71E+46	1.58E+22	1.78E+47
J0428.7-3755	BLLAC	LSP	2.11E+44	9.68E+45	2.13E+47	2.23E+47	1.47E+45	2.51E+13	2.45E+46	3.98E+23	3.58E+47
J0449.7-4348	BLLAC	HSP	8.22E+43	1.68E+44	1.83E+44	4.33E+44	2.45E+44	3.98E+15	5.78E+45	1.00E+24	3.93E+45
J0457.1-2325	FSRQ	LSP	4.11E+44	5.41E+45	1.40E+47	1.45E+47	3.30E+45	1.58E+13	2.33E+46	6.31E+22	5.58E+47
J0507.9+6739	BLLAC	HSP	4.99E+43	2.87E+44	5.55E+44	8.92E+44	2.63E+44	2.51E+16	7.19E+45	3.98E+24	5.65E+45
J0516.2-6200	BLLAC	LSP	5.25E+44	4.66E+45	1.10E+47	1.15E+47	1.81E+45	1.00E+13	2.59E+46	1.00E+23	2.26E+47
J0531.0+1331	FSRQ	LSP	5.79E+45	5.20E+45	2.75E+47	2.86E+47	2.69E+46	1.00E+13	1.46E+47	1.00E+22	3.93E+48
J0538.8-4403	BLLAC	LSP	7.51E+44	5.26E+45	8.14E+46	8.74E+46	3.59E+45	3.98E+13	7.33E+46	1.00E+23	3.68E+47
J0712.9+5034	BLLAC	LSP	1.55E+44	3.75E+44	3.40E+45	3.93E+45	2.15E+44	1.00E+14	2.90E+45	1.00E+23	6.58E+45
J0722.0+7120	BLLAC	ISP	4.68E+44	6.39E+44	2.89E+45	4.00E+45	8.17E+44	6.31E+14	2.92E+46	3.98E+22	1.37E+46
J0730.4-1142	FSRQ	LSP	8.98E+44	1.38E+46	4.39E+47	4.54E+47	7.89E+45	6.31E+12	7.25E+46	2.51E+22	1.87E+48
J0855.4+2009	BLLAC	LSP	1.04E+45	7.85E+44	1.10E+46	1.28E+46	4.66E+44	3.98E+13	1.95E+46	2.51E+22	8.14E+45
J0921.2+4437	FSRQ	LSP	6.21E+44	1.61E+46	2.79E+47	2.96E+47	5.00E+45	1.58E+13	1.15E+47	1.00E+23	8.15E+47
J1015.2+4927	BLLAC	HSP	5.00E+43	7.74E+43	1.04E+44	2.31E+44	3.41E+44	2.51E+16	3.33E+45	2.51E+24	3.00E+45
J1057.8+0138	BLLAC	LSP	4.58E+44	5.29E+45	1.11E+47	1.17E+47	5.79E+44	1.58E+13	2.91E+46	1.58E+23	5.36E+46
J1058.9+5629	BLLAC	ISP	1.27E+44	2.38E+43	1.85E+44	3.36E+44	4.71E+44	1.00E+15	8.31E+44	3.98E+22	6.66E+44
J1104.5+3811	BLLAC	HSP	4.82E+42	7.68E+43	2.51E+43	1.07E+44	1.82E+43	3.98E+16	6.62E+44	1.58E+25	3.02E+44
J1159.2+2912	FSRQ	LSP	2.03E+45	9.84E+44	1.78E+46	2.08E+46	1.70E+45	1.58E+13	2.91E+46	1.00E+22	1.17E+47
J1221.7+2814	BLLAC	ISP	6.54E+42	2.63E+44	7.37E+44	1.01E+45	3.85E+43	2.51E+15	5.81E+44	1.00E+24	6.22E+44
J1229.1+0202	FSRQ	LSP	2.36E+44	9.14E+44	9.93E+45	1.11E+46	1.74E+45	2.51E+13	1.01E+46	6.31E+21	1.73E+46
J1248.7+5811	BLLAC	ISP	2.46E+44	1.41E+45	4.28E+45	5.93E+45	1.30E+45	6.31E+14	4.11E+46	6.31E+22	4.15E+46
J1256.1-0548	FSRQ	LSP	1.74E+45	5.89E+45	5.05E+47	5.12E+47	9.11E+44	3.98E+12	3.88E+46	2.51E+22	8.97E+46
J1310.6+3220	FSRQ	LSP	3.80E+45	2.68E+45	6.88E+46	7.53E+46	2.99E+45	1.00E+13	8.06E+46	1.58E+22	3.97E+47
J1457.6-3538	FSRQ	LSP	1.88E+44	8.53E+45	1.18E+47	1.27E+47	1.11E+46	1.58E+13	3.24E+46	6.31E+22	1.21E+48
J1504.4+1030	FSRQ	LSP	2.79E+44	1.62E+46	1.66E+47	1.82E+47	1.95E+46	1.58E+13	7.55E+46	1.58E+23	5.20E+48
J1512.7-0905	FSRQ	LSP	1.80E+44	9.46E+44	1.35E+46	1.46E+46	2.19E+45	1.58E+13	4.52E+45	1.58E+22	9.34E+46
J1522.2+3143	FSRQ	LSP	2.11E+44	2.06E+45	3.19E+46	3.42E+46	1.25E+46	1.58E+13	8.28E+45	2.51E+22	1.07E+48
J1543.1+6130	BLLAC	ISP	9.22E+41	7.01E+44	7.04E+44	1.41E+45	6.78E+42	2.51E+14	2.10E+44	1.58E+23	2.61E+44
J1653.9+3946	BLLAC	HSP	2.37E+42	2.04E+43	1.27E+43	3.55E+43	1.27E+43	6.31E+16	1.30E+44	1.00E+25	5.86E+43
J1719.3+1746	BLLAC	LSP	1.27E+42	1.54E+45	1.43E+46	1.59E+46	3.03E+43	3.98E+13	1.32E+44	3.98E+23	1.48E+45
J1751.5+0935	BLLAC	LSP	3.05E+44	1.77E+45	8.91E+46	9.11E+46	2.57E+44	6.31E+12	4.23E+45	3.98E+22	1.60E+46
J1849.4+6706	FSRQ	LSP	3.74E+44	2.21E+45	4.29E+46	4.55E+46	9.39E+44	1.58E+13	1.29E+46	1.00E+23	7.22E+46
J2000.2+6506	BLLAC	HSP	1.15E+43	9.29E+42	4.37E+42	2.52E+43	6.94E+43	1.58E+17	3.90E+44	6.31E+24	1.50E+44
J2143.2+1741	FSRQ	LSP	5.44E+44	2.05E+44	6.96E+45	7.71E+45	2.79E+44	2.51E+13	2.33E+45	1.00E+22	4.59E+45
J2158.8-3014	BLLAC	HSP	9.58E+43	1.49E+44	2.92E+44	5.37E+44	1.72E+44	6.31E+15	4.67E+45	1.00E+24	2.11E+45
J2202.4+4217	BLLAC	ISP	1.61E+44	4.20E+43	3.95E+44	5.98E+44	2.44E+44	2.51E+14	9.21E+44	2.51E+21	3.90E+44
J2254.0+1609	FSRQ	LSP	9.07E+45	9.46E+45	3.02E+47	3.20E+47	1.72E+46	1.00E+13	4.54E+47	1.58E+22	3.65E+48
J2327.3+0947	FSRQ	LSP	5.13E+45	2.46E+45	1.55E+47	1.63E+47	1.29E+46	1.00E+13	5.83E+46	1.00E+22	1.70E+48
J2345.5-1559	FSRQ	LSP	4.38E+44	4.13E+44	6.38E+45	7.23E+45	1.28E+45	2.51E+13	4.24E+45	1.58E+22	6.53E+46

Chapter 6 Curvature and γ -ray Dominance of Fermi Blazars

The study of γ -ray emission of blazars plays an important role in understanding the jet physics (jet launching, energy dissipation and particle acceleration), the cosmic evolution history and the origin of ultra high energy cosmic rays (Kalashev et al., 2013; Madejski et al., 2016; MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2008; Massaro et al., 2015b; Plaga, 1995). The γ -rays can be explained as inverse Compton (IC) emission of accelerated electrons in the jet. The IC emission in BL Lacs arises due to internal synchrotron photons and called synchrotron self-Compton (SSC) (Abdo et al., 2011). The multi-wavelength catalog of blazars, Roma-BZCAT¹ v5.0, is the most comprehensive catalog in the literature, which contains 3561 confirmed blazars or candidates (Massaro et al., 2009, 2015a). Recently, Fermi Fourth LAT AGN Catalog (4LAC) presented a sample of nearly 3000 blazars or blazar candidates at high galactic latitude (Ajello et al., 2020). Therefore, there may be >500 blazars having not been detected with γ -ray emission (γ -ray quiet), although they have similar emission properties at lower energy wavelength bands (radio through X-ray) compared to γ -ray detected blazars. The origin of this discrepancy is not yet known. Many studies have focused on this question and found that γ -ray loud blazars have relatively large jet opening angle, larger apparent superluminal velocity and higher brightness temperature relative to γ -ray quiet blazars (Linfoord et al., 2012; Lister et al., 2016; Piner et al., 2012; Pushkarev et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2014). All these properties are attributed to a relativistic geometric effect - Doppler beaming effect. The smaller viewing angle in γ -ray loud blazars makes apparent larger jet opening angle and larger Doppler beaming factor, which give rise to larger apparent superluminal velocity and higher brightness temperature. In addition to this geometric effect, it is expected that the origin of the discrepancy between γ -ray loud versus γ -ray quiet blazars might be intrinsic. However, it is not yet known.

The spectral energy distribution (SED) of synchrotron emission is highly curved and presents a significant bump in $\nu - \nu F_\nu$ space, with peak frequency between infrared to

¹<http://www.asdc.asi.it/bzcat/>

X-rays (Chen et al., 2011; Ghisellini et al., 2015, 2014). The curvature of broadband SED of the synchrotron bump has a different value for blazars, which means that some SED bumps are broad while others are narrow (Chen, 2014, 2018). If the SED (broad band or single band) is fitted by a log-parabolic function, $\log \nu F_\nu = \log \nu_p F_{\nu_p} - \beta (\log \nu - \log \nu_p)^2$, the coefficient of the second order term b can be considered a "surrogate" to measure the curvature. It has been found that the radio and Fermi γ -ray flux positively correlate with each other. The blazars with higher radio flux may have broader synchrotron bump. It should be noted that the broadband curvature of a blazar is not changed with the transformation from observer to AGN frame (Cosmological redshift) and jet co-moving frame (Doppler beaming). However the single band curvature is effected due to Doppler effect causing the spectral shifts. In this work, I investigate the possible relation between γ -ray emission and the SED curvature for BL Lacs. The curvature in SED is produced due to an intrinsic curvature in the emitting electron energy distribution (EED) arising due to competition of particle acceleration and cooling (Kardashev, 1962; Tramacere et al., 2011), as shown in Section 3.2.

6.1 The 3LAC Sample Parameters

Based on 3LAC, Fan et al. (2016) collected available spectral data of 1392 blazars from NED² to build broadband SEDs of synchrotron bump and fitted them by a log-parabolic function. The synchrotron spectral curvature β , synchrotron frequency ν_{sp} , synchrotron flux F_{sp} , integrated γ -ray flux in 0.1-100 GeV band F_γ , and γ -ray band curvature β_γ have been compiled for confirmed 620 BL Lacs in 3LAC (Fan et al., 2016). Wu et al. (2007) presented the Doppler factors δ of a large radio loud BL Lac sample. Cross matching two catalogs, the spectral parameters and δ are compiled for a sample of total 170 BL Lacs.

6.2 FBLs versus NFBLs

A curved SED necessary suggests that the emitting EED should be intrinsically curved, arising from the stochastic nature of acceleration gain as explained in Section 3.1. Anjum et al. (2020) found that the such an acceleration mechanism is only manifested in BL Lacs, whereas FSRQs do not show any signature of acceleration. The synchrotron bump is particularly important and reveals the true curvature of broadband EED. Since

²<http://ned.ipac.caltech.edu/>

the accretion disk continuum emission in FSRQs are usually presented as a big blue bump at ultraviolet wavelength band, which can affect accurate measurement of the curvature parameter, only BL Lacs have been selected for purpose of our study. The selection of BL Lacs is further motivated by the fact that the high energy bump in FSRQs arises due to external Compton (EC) emission and, therefore, the curvature of IC bump may be related to the complex seed photon distribution and any absorption (Chen, 2014). The curvature of high energy bump in BL Lacs mimics the synchrotron curvature as it arises due to internal synchrotron seed photons (Massaro et al., 2006). However, it is hard to constrain the intrinsic of the EED solely from the IC bump, since the curvature of IC bump may depend on the IC cooling regime. Paggi et al. (2009) found that the IC curvature in Thomson regime is smaller than in Klein-Nishina regime. Therefore, synchrotron SED bump is used to constrain intrinsic curvature of EED $b \sim 5\beta$ (Massaro et al., 2006) in this work. The curvature of SED and γ -ray emission of BL Lacs is expected to be intrinsically related and can be used to investigate the origin of discrepancy between Fermi detected BL Lacs (FBLs) and non-detected ones (NFBLs).

A large amount of multi-wavelength data for the objects in the Metsähovi radio observatory BL Lac sample were collected by Nieppola et al. (2006), which have no selection criteria (other than declination) in addition to the ones in original surveys. The Metsähovi radio observatory BL Lac sample includes 381 objects selected from the Veron-Cetty & Veron BL Lac Catalog (Veron-Cetty et al., 2000), and 17 objects from the literature, of which many sources are from the well-known BL Lac samples like 1Jy, S4, S5, Einstein Medium Sensitivity Survey (EMSS), Einstein Slew Survey, and Deep X-Ray Radio Blazar Survey (DXRBS). Based on the multi-wavelength data, the SED of each source was constructed in the $\log \nu - \log \nu F_\nu$ representation and the synchrotron bump was fitted with a log-parabolic function (Nieppola et al., 2006) to determine spectral parameters. Based on this sample, Wu et al. (2007) collected the available data at 330 MHz, 360 MHz, 408 MHz, and 1.4 GHz from the Astrophysical Catalogs Support System (CATs) maintained by the Special Astrophysical Observatory, Russia, and the available VLA or MERLIN core and extended flux data, resulting in a sample of 170 BL Lacs. The low frequency radio power can be a reliable indicator of the intrinsic radio power, while the Doppler beaming can affect the observed radio power of the core (Giovannini et al., 2001; Giroletti et al., 2004). Therefore, with the VLA or MERLIN core and the 408 MHz luminosity, assum-

Figure 6.1 The curvature and Doppler beaming effect in BL Lacs. The dashed lines represent 4 bins of Doppler factor δ . The small points represent the values of individual sources, while the large points show the average value of curvature in each bin. The error bars correspond to one standard deviation of the average value.

ing a jet speed $\Gamma = 5$ consistent with Metsähovi radio monitoring studies (Lähteenmäki et al., 1999), the Doppler beaming factors have been estimated (Wu et al., 2007). The Doppler factors δ and curvature parameters of these 170 BL Lacs have been compiled. By cross correlating this sample with 3 LAC (Ackermann et al., 2015), 34 out of these 170 BL Lacs are not found to have γ -ray emission (NFBL). These NFBLs are: NRAO 5, NPM1G +41.0022, 1ES 0145+138, MS 0158.5+0019, MS 0257.9+3429, RXS J0314.0+2445, S5 0454+84, MS 0607.9+7108, B3 0651+428, 4C 22.21, RXS J0916.8+5238, B2 0927+35, RGB J0952+656, 1ES 1044+549, 1ES 1212+078, 1ES 1255+244, 1ES 1320+084N, MC 1400+162, MS 1407.9+5954, RGB J1427+541, MS 1443.5+6349, RXS J1516.7+2918, MS 1534.2+0148, RXS J1602.2+3050, RXS J1644.2+4546, RGB J1652+403, B3 1746+470, RXS J1750.0+4700, RGB J1811+442, PKS 2254+074, Q J2319+161, 1ES 2326+174, MS 2336.5+0517 and MS 2347.4+1924. The remaining 136 BL Lacs are, therefore, considered FBLs. Although many of these NFBLs might be detected in the 4LAC, however their γ -ray flux must be lower than the FBLs.

The SED of blazars is usually curved even in a single energy band. The Doppler factor changes cause the peak $\nu_p = \nu'_p \delta$ shifts of synchrotron and IC component, that affects the Fermi-LAT γ -ray band curvature β_γ . Accounting for the peak shifts due to Doppler boosting, the intrinsic difference of curvature may account for discrepancy between FBLs and NFBLs. We plot curvature parameter (in $1/b$) against δ for FBLs and NFBLs in Figure 6.1, which shows that both FBLs and NFBLs overlap but the curvature of FBLs

Figure 6.2 The distribution and the cumulative fractions of FBLs vs NFBLs. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test yields the significance level probability for the null hypothesis that FBLs and NFBLs are drawn from the same distribution $P = 5.87 \times 10^{-5}$ and the statistic (the maximum separation of the two cumulative fractions) $D_{KS} = 0.43$.

would be on average smaller than that of NFBLs. We binned the data in $\log(\delta)$ and find the average value of curvature in each bin, represented by big circles in Figure 6.1. Due to only one NFBL in the last bin, we consider it as the average curvature value. FBLs, on average, seem to have smaller curvature (higher value of $1/b$) and, thus, broader SED than NFBLs.

In order to eliminate effect of Doppler beaming as much as possible, a new parameter $\beta - \log \delta$ is artificially defined, that roughly measures the curvature given the same beaming factor. Figure 6.2 shows the distributions of $\beta - \log \delta$ and cumulative fraction of FBLs and NFBLs. It can be seen that statistically FBLs have relative smaller values of $\beta - \log \delta$ than that of NFBLs, which confirm the above finding that smaller curvature of synchrotron SED bump is attributed to larger γ -ray power. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test yields the significance level probability for the null hypothesis that FBLs and NFBLs are drawn from the same distribution $P = 5.87 \times 10^{-5}$, and the maximum separation of the two cumulative fractions is $D_{KS} = 0.43$. The TeV BL Lacs (TBLs) with synchrotron peak frequency $\nu_s > 10^{15}$ Hz showed a similar behavior (Massaro et al., 2011b). Massaro et al. (2011b) and Massaro et al. (2013) found X-ray band curvature of TBLs to be systematically smaller than that of non-detected at TeV energies. They suggested that X-ray flux can be used as a predictor for TeV γ -ray detection of BL Lacs. However the TeV spectral curvature may not correspond to X-ray curvature, as the TeV emission is significantly attenuated by EBL. Since GeV γ -ray emission is not absorbed, I argue that it can provide better constraint on TeV detection as compared to X-rays.

Figure 6.3 Broadband SEDs of PKS 0048-09 and S5 0716+714. Quasi-simultaneous data points are presented as large squares (PKS 0048-09) and circles (S5 0716+714), while the small ones show the non-simultaneous data. The solid lines represent the synchrotron+SSC model curves. Both sources have same jet parameters other than size R and curvature b , assuming $b \propto R$.

6.3 SED Curvature and γ -ray Dominance

Although blazars are highly variable sources, the variability is more prominent at higher energies. The short variability times at higher energies can be explained due to cooling. However the $CD \sim L_{\text{cp}}/L_{\text{sp}}$ is an important parameter and related to energy density of magnetic field u_B or radiation energy density u_r . Therefore, CD may reveal the source conditions which affect particle acceleration and cooling.

The fact that synchrotron SED is significantly curved inevitably implies a curvature in the steady electron energy distribution $N(\gamma)$ as a PL EED yields a PL SED. This curvature may be a result of particle cooling and acceleration which might be relevant on different times. A more efficient acceleration of stochastic type makes energy distribution electrons relatively broader, manifested by a smaller curvature (Tramacere et al., 2011). A higher acceleration efficiency implies a lesser time ($t = R/c$) spent in acceleration region by the particles and large number of acceleration steps, which corresponds to a smaller size of the acceleration/emission region (Massaro et al., 2011a). Therefore, the spectral curvature of EED is expected to be proportional to the size of blazar region. As the γ -rays from BL Lacs are believed to be (SSC) emission of the same non-thermal electron population emitting low energy synchrotron emission, a smaller size would enhance the synchrotron seed photons energy density $u_s = L_s/4\pi R^2 c \delta^4$ in the jet, that would lead to higher Compton dominance parameter $CD = u_s/u_B$, i.e, a higher relative γ -ray power. This implies that among the BL Lacs with same a synchrotron luminosity L_s , the source

with relatively high γ -ray dominance may have relatively compact emission region.

Abdo et al. (2010a) provided broadband simultaneous or quasi-simultaneous spectral data from radio through γ -rays, of 48 LBAS blazars, as mentioned in Section 5.2. The example of SEDs of two BL Lacs PKS 0048-09 and S5 0716+714 is shown in Figure 6.3. These sources have similar synchrotron luminosity and peak frequency but different γ -ray power, i.e., the Compton dominance. The S5 0716+714 included 3 observations at optical and X-ray bands during those three months (Abdo et al., 2010a). The average value of fluxes for this BL Lac has been used. I use standard one-zone SSC model (Chen, 2017; Ghisellini et al., 2014; Kang et al., 2014; Yan et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2014), described in Section 5.1, to fit their SEDs. In order to keep accordance with log-parabolic shape of synchrotron SED, the emitting particles are assumed to be leptons with energy distribution following a log-parabolic function,

$$N(\gamma) = N_0 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} \right)^{-3} 10^{-b \log(\gamma/\gamma_0)^2}, \quad (6.1)$$

where b measures the curvature of number distribution of electron energy. As discussed above, the curvature may be proportional to the size of emission region in the SSC model. Therefore, in our calculation, the curvature parameter is assumed to be proportional to the radius of the emission sphere, i.e., $b \propto R$. The calculated SEDs are also presented in the Figure 6.3. It seems interesting that both SEDs can be well fitted with same jet parameters except for the radii of emission sphere $R_{0048} = 2.8 \times 10^{16}$ cm and $R_{0716} = 5.0 \times 10^{16}$ cm for PKS 0048-09 and S5 0716+714 (and therefore the curvature $b_{0048} = 0.5$ and $b_{0716} = (R_{0716}/R_{0048}) b_{0048} = 0.89$) respectively. The other constant jet parameters are the magnetic field strength $B = 0.15$ G, the Doppler factor $\delta = 24$, the peak electron energy $\gamma_0 = 8660$ and the normalized total electron numbers $N_0 = 6.8 \times 10^{45}$. This modeling example illustrates that a higher γ -ray luminosity intrinsically accompanies a smaller curvature, which may be related to a smaller size of emission region and the processes governing the jet micro-physics, i.e., particle acceleration and cooling. This is further consistent with the fact that bright γ -ray blazars are more (rapidly) variable than γ -ray weak blazars from studying γ -ray and optical variability of a sample blazars (Hovatta et al., 2014; Vovk et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2016), possibly due to smaller size of emission region and/or larger Doppler beaming factor in bright sources. Figure 6.3 shows that among the BL Lacs with a given synchrotron peak luminosity and frequency, the object with the highest CD might have smaller curvature (i.e., hard spectrum). A higher

Figure 6.4 The synchrotron peak frequency ν_{sp} versus Compton dominance CD of BL Lacs. The solid line shows the best linear fit.

CD coupled with a lower curvature favor the detection of a blazar by Fermi. Therefore, I argue that CD and curvature β both are important parameters for Fermi detection.

Since both the cooling and a stochastic acceleration can lead to a curved EED/SED with a peak energy γ_p , this raises the question about the origin of peak $\nu_{\text{sp}} \propto \gamma_p^2 B \delta$ and its evolution in BL Lacs. In a pure cooling scenario, a PL electron distribution injected in the blazar cooling zone will lead to a steady broken power-law (BPL) EED, with indices p_1 and p_2 before and after the break energy γ_p , due to cooling and particle escape. In a purely acceleration, a log-parabolic EED is obtained with the peak energy

$$\log \gamma_p = \log \gamma_0 + \frac{3 - a}{2b} \quad (6.2)$$

and curvature b . Thus a curved and peaked EED/SED can be obtained in both mechanisms, however curvature changes significantly in a stochastic acceleration. Blazars usually show an inverse correlation between synchrotron peak ν_{sp} and Compton dominance (CD) known as blazar sequence. The ν_{sp} and CD have been collected for ~ 280 BL Lacs from 3LAC to study the origin of peak. Figure 6.4 shows that ν_{sp} is anti-correlated with CD, which is known as blazar sequence. Thus it is suggested that although the curvature of EED/SED arises mainly due to a stochastic acceleration component the peak energy is a cooling break, as manifested by blazar cooling sequence.

6.4 The γ -ray Curvature and Future Prospects

Interestingly the Fermi-LAT GeV γ -ray spectra are curved similarly as observed in the X-ray bands. [Ackermann et al. \(2015\)](#) found that the LAT spectra of ~ 160 bright blazars can be well fitted with log-parabolic model. The number of blazars with log-parabolic spectra

Figure 6.5 The curvature of Fermi detected blazars. The left panel shows the γ -ray energy flux F_γ against curvature β_γ with dashed line deviding the 3LAC and 4LAC samples. The right panel shows the source detection significance σ against β_γ .

Figure 6.6 Distribution of synchrotron curvature β (left panel) and γ -ray curvature β_γ (right panel) of blazars.

increased to >700 in the 4LAC (Ajello et al., 2020). Figure 6.5 shows that the number of blazars with consistent log-parabolic shape is significantly increased from 3LAC to 4LAC and the brighter sources manifest smaller curvature (i.e., broader spectra). The right panel of Figure 6.5 shows that the blazars detected with higher significance (σ) level have relatively broader spectra. The broader (smaller curvature β_γ) when brighter trend has also been observed in the X-rays band (Massaro et al., 2004a, 2008). Figure 6.5 suggests that broader when brighter may be a general feature of blazars, and that γ -ray spectra of all blazars might be intrinsically curved spectra if detected at high σ level (see Kang et al., 2018).

The Figure 6.6 shows that synchrotron and γ -ray curvature for FSRQs is higher, on average, than BL Lacs, that may be related to different physical conditions in the jet. This is consistent with the results obtained in Chapter 5, that showed BL Lac have a strong

Figure 6.7 Comparisons of the differential sensitivity of CTA-south and -north (left) and LHAASO (right) with existing Cherenkov telescopes. The left panel taken from (Cherenkov Telescope Array Consortium et al., 2019), while the right panel from (di Sciacio et al., 2016).

stochastic acceleration component which leads to relatively smaller curvature than FSRQs.

The GeV γ -ray curvature is particularly important as it connects with the TeV emission. Till now, only 76 blazars are detected in VHE γ -rays³ with majority of them being BL Lacs. As more blazars would be detected in the VHE band by imaging atmospheric Cherenkov telescopes (IACTs), e.g., High Energy Stereoscopic System (H.E.S.S.)⁴, and future γ -ray observatories including Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA)⁵ and Large High Altitude Air Shower Observatory (LHAASO)⁶, the study of origin of VHS emission and its curvature can lead to a better understanding of radiative cooling and particle acceleration mechanisms and the spectral evolution of emitting particle distribution in the jets. Fermi 4LAC based on the 8 years exposure provided a large sample of blazar in broad energy coverage from 50 MeV to 1 TeV (Ajello et al., 2020), however LAT onboard Fermi is only efficient detector in the MeV-GeV energy range. The upcoming CTA is the highly sensitive in the GeV-TeV range, as shown in the left panel of Figure 6.7. Its higher sensitivity and minute timescale capability of CTA are particularly important for study of variable TeV γ -rays blazar emission up to higher redshifts. The CTA provides broader energy coverage from 20 GeV to 300 TeV (Cherenkov Telescope Array Consortium et al., 2019), however LHAASO is more sensitive especially from few tens of TeV up to 1 PeV, as shown in right panel of Figure 6.7. The LHAASO is a system of three detectors (Cao,

³<http://tevcat.uchicago.edu/>

⁴<https://www.mpi-hd.mpg.de/hfm/HESS/>

⁵<https://www.cta-observatory.org/>

⁶<http://english.ihep.cas.cn/lhaaso/>

2010): a 1 km² array of 1146 underground water tanks for muon detection (KM2A) with a sensitivity of about 1% Crab Unit at 100 TeV energy; a surface water wide Cherenkov detector array (WCDA) which is a survey facility from 100 GeV to 20 TeV; and an array of 12 wide-field-of-view Cherenkov telescopes (WFCA).

Together CTA-North and LHAASO survey will provide the details of γ -ray sky from 20 GeV up to ~ 1 PeV energy in the northern hemi-sphere at an unprecedented level. In this thesis, the higher energy bump of the blazar SED is assumed to be a purely leptonic IC component, however hadronic processes might be important in TeV sources. Therefore it is important to study the origin of curvature and its evolution in the blazars in a more physical scenario. The synergy between GeV and TeV band will provide the high quality spectral data to constrain the models of emission, particle acceleration and EBL. Thus, the future prospects of study on particle acceleration and origin of curvature in blazar SEDs depends on the data provided by CTA and LHAASO observatories.

Chapter 7 Summary and Conclusions

The blazar SEDs are significantly curved and show a sharp peak in the νF_ν space. It is not clear how the spectral peak and the curvature are related to each other and evolve in the blazar jets in a combined stochastic acceleration and cooling scenario. First I investigated the properties of curvature and its evolution in Fermi blazars by modeling the broadband quasi-simultaneous SEDs of a complete sample of 48 blazars. It is found that a one-zone log-parabolic IC model can successfully explain the simultaneous broadband SEDs self-consistently. The SSC emission can explain the high energy emission in IBLs and HBLs, whereas an EC component is inevitably important to explain the emission of FSRQs and LBLs at GeV energies, as in previous studies (e.g., [Dermer et al., 2014](#); [Zhang et al., 2013](#), and references therein). The EC emission mainly comes from the dusty torus, however the contribution of BLR is important in some sources, suggesting that the γ -ray location may be at the edge of BLR. The external seed photon energy density required to explain the γ -ray emission is significantly lower in some cases as compared to a constant value derived from the reverberation mapping of BLR and dusty torus. The physical parameters of blazars systematically change while moving LSP sources toward HSP source along the blazar sequence. The magnetic field B in blazars decreases continuously from FSRQs toward HBLs, suggesting that jets in FSRQs have slightly higher magnetization. Similar to B , the curvature parameter $b \sim 5\beta$ decreases systematically in blazars from FSRQs towards HBLs through IBLs. The blazars show a theoretical blazar sequence between jet power and the electron peak energy. A systematic trend of curvature and physical parameters values changing from one SED class to another suggests that SED curvature is an important parameter of blazar sequence in addition to synchrotron peak frequency and luminosity. It is found that curvature in the EED, that originates due to a stochastic component in the underlying acceleration mechanism, evolves against peak energy γ_p differently in BL Lacs and FSRQs due to different ambient conditions. In BL Lacs, the curvature evolves in an acceleration dominated regime and cooling is of secondary importance or practically irrelevant. The nature of acceleration seems to be hard-sphere, since the curvature anti-correlates well with the γ_p for a broad range of γ_p . The curvature in FSRQs evolves in a transition regime where the cooling overtakes the stochastic

acceleration and conditions nearly correspond to a steady state. Our results are consistent with theoretical predictions of [Tramacere et al. \(2011\)](#), i.e, the curvature decreases continuously in the acceleration regime and grows mildly or remains nearly steady in cooling dominated regime. The strong cooling in FSRQs is also manifested by the fact that their γ_p varies in a small range as compared to BL Lacs. This happens in FSRQs as the cooling timescale at peak energy γ_p quickly gets shorter than the typical acceleration timescale due relatively higher magnetic field and the additional EC component. Thus, a higher jet energy density in FSRQs restricts the growth of γ_p and provides the extra curvature at the high energy tail of EED. This explains why, on the average, FSRQs have higher curvature compared to BL Lacs and their peak energy varies in a small range. A similar trend for BL Lacs and FSRQs in 4LAC is seen, even for a single energy band from 50 MeV to 1 TeV. This shows that curvature in BL Lacs and FSRQs evolve differently due to different physical conditions. Although blazars detected in 4LAC with a log-parabolic spectra are $< 20\%$, these sources are very bright with average significance of detection $\sigma > 40$. This suggests that all blazars may have intrinsically curved spectra ([Ajello et al., 2020](#); [Kang et al., 2018](#)). Since the Fermi-LAT spectra usually do not show the signature of internal absorption ([Costamante et al., 2018](#)), the observed spectral curvature must be related to an intrinsic curvature in emitting EED.

I also studied the intrinsic origin of why are some BL Lacs are detected to have γ -ray emission but not all. It is found that the SED curvature and the γ -ray dominance (or Compton dominance) of BL Lacs might is related. I selected 170 BL Lacs from the literature with measured synchrotron curvature b and Doppler factor δ , and divide them into 136 FBLs and 34 NFBLs based on Fermi 3LAC. It is found that FBLs show smaller curvature (i.e., broader SED) than NFBLs even after getting rid of the beaming effect. It is suggested that the γ -ray power and the curvature might be related. An example of two Fermi BL Lacs PKS 0048-09 and S5 0716+714, having similar synchrotron peak frequency and luminosity but different Compton dominance, is presented. The PKS 0048-09 shows relatively higher Compton dominance as compared to S5 0716+714. Within a one-zone SSC model, it is found that their quasi-simultaneous SEDs can be well fitted by log-parabolic SSC model with same physical jet parameters except for the size of emission region and EED curvature (assuming curvature being proportional to the size). The PKS 0048-09 manifest relatively smaller source size and a smaller curvature as compared to

S5 0716+714. These results imply that, for a given synchrotron power, the Compton dominant blazars may have smaller curvature and account for the discrepancy between FBLs and NFBLs. The positive relationship between the source size and curvature is explained in a combined scenario of cooling and stochastic acceleration. A compact jet demands an efficient stochastic acceleration. As the emitting particles have less time to spend in the source, the acceleration gain or number of acceleration steps should be large. Thus, a more efficient stochastic acceleration in compact jets in FBLs makes the EED relatively broader due to an efficient acceleration. However, a smaller source size, in turn, implies a higher photon energy density in the jet, yielding a higher γ -ray dominance for a similar synchrotron power. Therefore at a given synchrotron luminosity, the FBLs may have intrinsically compact jets, showing smaller curvature and higher γ -ray dominance as compared NFBLs. Both acceleration and cooling can lead to a curved EED/SED. The BL Lacs show a signature of blazar sequence between Compton dominance (CD) and synchrotron peak frequency (ν_p), suggesting that although the curvature in EED arises due to stochastic acceleration the peak energy γ_p is controlled by cooling.

It is important to study the origin and evolution of curvature in blazar jets in a more realistic scenario in which processes including injection, particle acceleration, radiative cooling, and particle escape compete against each other. The VHE γ -ray spectra are very important since it reveals the true curvature of EED at high energy tail. In this regard, the high quality spectral data from future missions VHE γ -ray observatories, e.g., CTA and LHAASO will be very useful. It is also important to compile big samples of γ -ray detected vs. non-detected blazars to study the origin of this discrepancy in context of particle acceleration and cooling mechanisms.

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Reference

The references can be provided on request.

List of Publications

Following research papers were published during the doctoral degree studies at UCAS.

Muhammad S. Anjum, Liang Chen, Minfeng Gu, 2020, On the Origin and Evolution of Curvature of the Spectral Energy Distribution of Fermi Bright Blazars[J], ApJ, 898:48

Muhammad S. Anjum, Liang Chen, Minfeng Gu, 2020, The Curvature of Spectral Energy Distribution and γ -ray Dominance of Fermi BL Lac Objects[J], Progress in Astronomy, accepted for publication

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